

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research
infrastructure PLUS

Common requirements for piloting of data workflows

Deliverable D10.3

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Authors involved in WP10 contributed to the eLTER frame conditions, the identification of data workflows for the eLTER RI and reviewed the existing EOSC and RI data workflows for the state of the art, with the support from authors of WP11 and WP4. They also collected and compiled the workflow use cases from the Science Cases of the four Research Challenges. Authors from the Research Challenge Science Cases (mainly from WP8 and WP9) provided information and specifications of their data workflows. Where relevant, the main authors of a chapter are provided.

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Abbreviations

ABM	Agent Based Modelling
API	Application Programming Interface
BDL	eLTER Research Challenge Biodiversity loss
BGC	eLTER Research Challenge Biogeochemical processes
CDN	Central Data Node
CI	Cyberinfrastructure
CWF	eLTER Research Challenge Climate-Water-Food Nexus
DAR	Digital Asset Register
DataLab	eLTER Virtual research environment
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System – Site and Dataset Registry
DIP	Data Integration Platform
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DP	Data Product
DRF	eLTER Data Reporting Format
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
eLTER RI	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
EnvThes	Environmental Thesaurus
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ETL	Extract/Transform/Load process
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GET	General Executive Team of the project
GEO	Group of Earth Observations
GEOSS	GEO System of Systems
HO	Head Office
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICP	International Cooperative Programme
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe
INSPIRE EF	INSPIRE Environmental Monitoring Facility
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
IT	Information Technology
MD	Metadata
NC	National LTER Network Coordinator
NRI	National Research Infrastructure
O&M	Observation & Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

OGC SOS	OGC Sensor Observation Service
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifiers
PN	Partner data Node
POP	Persistent Organic Pollutants
QA/QC	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
RA	Remote Access
RC	Research Challenge
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROR	Research ORganisation ID
RS	Remote Sensing
SC	Science Case
SDP	eLTER Standard Data Product
SES	eLTER Research Challenge Socio-Ecological Systems
SITES	Swedish Infrastructure for Ecosystem Science
SO	Standard Observations
SPC	Site and Platform Coordinator
SPF	Site and Platform coordinator Forum
SQL	Structured Query Language
SysML	System Modelling Language
TA	Transnational Access
TC	Topic Centre
TSA	Thematic Service Area
UID	Unique Identifier
UML	Unified Modelling Language
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VA	Virtual Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WAILS	Whole System Approach for in-situ research on Life Supporting Systems
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Warehouse Management System
WP	Work Package
WUE	Water Use Efficiency

Summary

Progress in understanding, managing, and securing current and future ecosystem functions and services is challenged by fragmented and dispersed ecosystem research. As the topic is often approached using narrow disciplinary perspectives, a holistic understanding of complex ecological and socio-ecological systems is needed in order to address environmental challenges and derive actions from this knowledge. The emerging European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI) aims to address this issue in the ecosystem and biodiversity domain, thereby closing this gap in the European RI landscape.

The primary objective of eLTER PLUS is to open and expand the research capacities and impact of eLTER by engaging current and new users and facilitating cross- and transdisciplinary research, exemplified in eLTER Site and Platform design and the RI's Standard Observation framework. eLTER PLUS is executing a performance test of the emerging RI and assessing and strengthening its operations in real time.

Within the current work, we analysed requirements for building data related workflows that enable the ingestion and publication of the eLTER data space. We also reviewed relevant Research Infrastructures and research networks to include best practices into the eLTER data management design. Based on the interaction with the Science Cases and the evaluation of the deliverables of the eLTER PLUS project, we identified a number of data related workflows. The deliverable describes the outcomes of the work and provides draft workflows for (a) the acquisition and access to historic and legacy data from eLTER facilities, (b) the access and extraction of relevant EO information, (c) the access and extraction of relevant third-party data, (d) the prototyping of data products for eLTER, and (e) the provision of SO conformant data to the central eLTER facilities. All workflows are described following a basic schema and are modelled with a generic activity diagram.

The collection of the requirements on the workflows is only the first step. In the final phase of the project, selected workflows will be used and implemented to develop eLTER Data Products.

1 Introduction

Providing quality controlled and reliable data as the basis for scientific analysis and as input into the construction of new and evaluation of existing environmental policies is one of the major aims of long-term ecosystem monitoring and research not only in Europe (Mirtl, 2010) but also on a global scale (Mirtl et al., 2018). In order to foster information exchange and sharing, data must be discoverable and at least the metadata accessible (Michener et al., 1997), accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR, Wilkinson et al., 2016). This requires proper documentation of data and services as well as the existence of infrastructure allowing the discovery and access of data in a web-based environment. One of the goals of LTER is to improve comparability of long-term ecological data and facilitate exchange and preservation of these data (Vanderbilt et al., 2015).

One of the challenges to be addressed in the implementation of the eLTER RI is to enable access to data across the site network. Based on the collection of data and ICT requirements (Peterseil et al., 2020b), we aim to select and identify common workflows relevant for the specification of the eLTER Information System and the related services and components. This addresses not only new data collections based on the Standard Observations (SO, Zacharias et al., 2021) but also on mobilising and ingesting historic and legacy data collected at the different eLTER sites (Peterseil et al., 2022). In the eLTER PLUS project, WP10 aims to support the establishment of the RI data services by collecting and defining requirements for data acquisition, data quality control, and analytical workflows to answer key research questions for Research Infrastructure (RI) users (Peterseil et al., 2020b), facilitate and support Virtual Access (VA), Transnational Access (TA), and Remote Access (RA), as well as liaise with WP11 to trial the use of new data workflows as data services from eLTER Central Data Node (CDN) and for user web access through the extended eLTER discovery portal.

Starting from the collection of data and ICT requirements (Peterseil et al., 2020b), the current work focuses on the identification of data related workflows to enable data integration and analysis. Within eLTER PLUS, we work towards the implementation of data products (DP) and identifying common requirements for related workflows. One of the guiding principles for the eLTER RI is to manage and store the raw observation data as rich as possible and store it in its original format to ensure transparency and reproducibility of the workflows applied in the context of the Research Infrastructure.

Within the eLTER PLUS project, we narrow the scope for the eLTER RI to data related workflows aiming to produce meaningful data for the user community of the eLTER RI and network. In this respect, in general a workflow can be defined as *a series of activities that are necessary to complete a task*. These workflow steps (or process steps) are in sequence with a clearly defined flow and direction. Also, DataCite's metadata schema (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2021) has a tag and definition for a workflow which defines a research workflow as *"a structured series of steps which can be executed to produce a final outcome, allowing users a means to specify and enact their work in a more reproducible manner."*

More specifically, a scientific data workflow can be defined as a series of steps or processes involved in collecting, managing, processing, analysing, and sharing scientific data. It is a systematic approach to research to ensure that data are properly managed, analysed, and reported, and that results can be replicated and validated by others. A typical scientific data workflow involves the following stages:

- Data collection - this encompasses the collection of data from various sources, such as experiments, surveys, or simulations. The data may be in different formats, such as text, images, or numerical values.
- Data management - this involves organising the data and storing it in a secure and accessible way. This involves cleaning the data, removing errors and inconsistencies, documentation of the data

cleaning procedures and ensuring that the data are properly labelled, annotated and described with rich metadata. First level of quality assurance and control will be dedicated to the data collector and provider. Second level quality control will be implemented when ingesting data to the central data management workflows.

- Data processing - this involves transforming the data into a format that can be analysed. This may involve filtering the data (e.g., based on thematic, spatial, temporal criteria), aggregating it, or converting it into a different format and collecting or capturing documentation of the process.
- Data analysis - this encompasses analysis and/or modelling of the data. This may involve exploratory data analysis, hypothesis testing, or predictive modelling.
- Reporting and visualisation - this involves presenting the results of the analysis in a clear and understandable way, using tables, charts, or other visualisations.
- Sharing, publishing and archiving - this involves sharing the data and the results of the analysis with the researchers, who provided the data, and archiving the original raw data as well as the processed data products along with the documentation in a repository or database for future use.
- Data Citation - this involves the identification of data and code using persistent identifiers (PID) enabling referencing the data and ensuring reproducibility.

Clearly defined scientific data workflows are important to ensure that data is properly managed and analysed, and that results are transparent and reproducible. It also helps to ensure that scientific research is conducted in an ethical and responsible way, and that research findings are trustworthy and reliable. By this, main aspects of the FAIR recommendations are addressed and need to be included within the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Research Infrastructure.

1.1 Project context

Progress in understanding, managing, and securing current and future ecosystem functions and services is challenged by fragmented and dispersed ecosystem research. As the topic is often approached using narrow disciplinary perspectives, a holistic understanding of complex ecological and socio-ecological systems is hampered and sometimes prevented. The emerging European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI)¹ aims to close this gap in the European RI landscape by addressing the ecosystem: biodiversity, biogeochemical and socio-ecological domains.

The eLTER PLUS² project aims to open and expand the research capacities and impact of eLTER by engaging current and new users and facilitating cross- and transdisciplinary research, exemplified in the eLTER Site and Platform design and the development of the RI's Standard Observation framework (Zacharias et al., 2021). eLTER PLUS makes use of selected sites and platforms in terrestrial, freshwater, and coastal ecosystems and facilitates observational data in order to enable the analysis of ecosystem and socio-ecological responses to globally relevant environmental challenges in terms of ecosystem integrity and ecosystem services. Applying a Whole-Systems approach (WAILS) (Mirtl et al., 2021), eLTER derives meaningful scientific and policy relevant information via co-designed, transdisciplinary research in collaboration with diverse stakeholders at local, regional, and EU-scales. Concerted actions also focus on collaboration with peer RIs (e.g., ICOS) to maximise synergies, increase efficiencies, and catalyse holistic understanding of ecosystem function, and on development of virtual laboratories where in-situ site data are linked with other data sources, e.g., Copernicus.

¹ See <https://elter-ri.eu/about-elter-ri>

² See <https://elter-ri.eu/elter-plus>

Within the eLTER PLUS project, a performance testing of the emerging eLTER RI and assessing and strengthening its operations in real time is executed. The project works towards a further integration of existing services for the LTER community and the eLTER RI, linking requirements not only from the current project, but addressing wider research infrastructure needs. Focusing on the requirements both in terms of data and service needs is a core task within the project.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the project design, showing the interlinkages between the different activities, which are fed by a number of processes, internal of and external to, the current project. The right side of the figure highlights the input by scientific and other user communities driving exemplary thematic Science Cases (SCs). The project outcomes, related to communities' requirements and developments feed into the eLTER European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) process, as represented on the left side of Figure 1. Synthesis and networking activities (e.g., WP2, 3, 5, and 6) link project outcomes, related communities' requirements and the development of eLTER Information Clusters (WP4), as shown in the top part, within the eLTER PLUS project. These activities occur in parallel to a strategically driven site selection process based on the existing eLTER site pool for the use of the site infrastructure for Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) research and data-use opportunities, as well as providing access to data and services from these sites via Virtual Access (VA).

Figure 1. The core concept of eLTER PLUS (Source: eLTER PLUS Proposal)

This includes also the facilitation of data from the supporting sites in order to generate data workflows and data products as a result of the eLTER network and the upcoming RI. Within the current project, an assessment of potential data workflows was conducted in order to draw recommendations and requirements for the development of the eLTER Information System and the governance of the data streams.

In collaboration with the INFRAIA Starting Community project eLTER PPP³, eLTER PLUS supports the building, prototyping and provisioning of services and facilitates the establishment of the eLTER RI as part of the ESFRI implementation process.

³ see <https://elter-ri.eu/elter-ppp>

1.2 Aim of the document

The current work is within the frame of WP10 focusing on the definition of core data and ICT needs as well as piloting data workflows in a schematic manner. Implementation of these workflows is done either by the specific Science Cases or in collaboration with WP11, dealing with service piloting and dissemination of data products. The main objectives of WP10 are:

- establish the RI data service functions and access portal requirements for data acquisition, data quality control and analytical workflows to answer key research questions for RI users and link to the eLTER research challenges and Science Cases (task 10.1);
- facilitate and support of Virtual Access (VA), Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) as well as WP11 to trial the use of new data workflows as data services from eLTER CDN and for user web access through the extended eLTER DIP (task 10.2); as well as to
- create synthesised ICT requirements for standard data products created by the RC case studies (Task 10.3).

The work on task 10.2 aims to evaluate, prioritise and pilot selected data workflows. Based on the data and ICT needs (Peterseil et al., 2020b), we identified and described relevant data workflows related to the RCs implemented in the project frame. Within the current activities, we focused on collecting common requirements for the processing steps from data management to data citation. Workflows addressing the collection of data are not considered in detail and are subject of the further specification of the Standard Observations (Zacharias et al., 2021).

Chapter 2 aims to set the frame conditions for the identification of the workflows. This encompasses the current design and implementation of software components and architecture as well as the data related characteristics. Chapter 3 summarises the approach to collect and document the workflows using activity diagrams. The resulting draft eLTER workflows are documented in Chapter 4 including reference to the activity diagrams using diagram.net (see footnotes). This includes an overview on workflows from related Research Infrastructures and observation networks which we evaluated in the scope of the task.

In Annex A - Science Case workflows, we provide a more detailed description of the prototype data product workflows developed together with the Science Cases. This text was moved to the annex to reduce the length of the main deliverable. Nevertheless, this information is important in the context of the deliverable. Annex B - State of the art - detailed description provides a more detailed description of the research infrastructures and observation networks surveyed for the development of the workflows.

2 eLTER Frame Conditions

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2.1 eLTER Research Challenges

To enhance the infrastructure services of LTER networks and utilise existing data and pilot data flows, four Research Challenges (RC) related to biodiversity loss (BDL), biogeochemical processes (BGC), hydrological processes (CWF, climate-water-food nexus), and socio-ecological processes (SES) have been defined in the project. Within these RCs, we aim to demonstrate the capabilities of data-rich LTER Sites in tackling these challenges and to apply a holistic approach and cross-site analysis. Data needs have been identified (Peterseil et al., 2020b), informing the selection and definition of eLTER

Standard Observations (Zacharias et al., 2021). These efforts aim to advance cross-site and cross-scale analyses within the eLTER RI framework. For each of the RCs, Science Cases (SC) have been selected, which are used to prototype and pilot selected data workflows.

2.2 eLTER Standard Observations

Based on eLTER's whole system approach, the eLTER Standard Observations (SOs) include the minimum set of variables and the associated methods and protocols that can characterise adequately the state and future trends of the Earth systems. SOs provide the basic information to determine the system's state and development and, furthermore, have a high impact, high feasibility, relatively low cost of implementation, and sufficient spatiotemporal coverage. The more specific requirements for the SOs are an ability to characterise an environmental system or process that can be generated and archived in an affordable way, relying on coordinated observation systems and proven current technology. SOs can be seen also as a part of the harmonisation process providing most critical information from the diverse primary observations in a standard format. In this sense, SOs have some commonalities with definitions of Essential Variables as developed in various scientific disciplines. On the one hand, they take into account the academic-scientific perspective on the most comprehensive description of states and fluxes possible in the environmental system under consideration, as is also reflected in concepts of Essential Variables. On the other hand, however, the definition is aligned with the design of the eLTER RI by considering aspects of cost-effectiveness and operative feasibility, as preconditions in the consideration of methods and protocols.

The SOs are critical for the design of the network and the overall services eLTER RI will provide. Cross-site and cross-habitat compliant standardised SOs will enable the integration of measurements from plot to continental scales as required to address the eLTER Research Challenges. An essential element of the hierarchy of eLTER site categories is the mandatory scope of in-situ data. In order to be applicable at eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms across European environments and socio-ecological regions, the specification of the SOs requires thorough consideration of habitat-specific requirements (what might be a "must" in forest, might not be feasible or reasonable for aquatic sites). Accordingly, a habitat-specific definition of core sets of eLTER SOs was made. (i) habitat-specific SO requirements related to the site category and (ii) information on methods, protocols and costs for each SO, provide the essential information to make a first analysis of the possible design of the future eLTER RI site network from the perspectives of the individual sites, the national networks as well as from a European perspective with respect to the eLTER site categories.

2.3 eLTER IT Components and services

The eLTER IT infrastructure aims to provide the facilities to store, describe, discover, explore, assess, and access information on long-term ecological observations and experimentation from across the eLTER network (Koivula et al., 2022), and forms the basis for the implementation of the skeleton RI. Due to the federated and distributed nature of the community, the eLTER IS seeks to support and enable flexibility to create new partner virtual data nodes where necessary. This includes the use of standardised services to link to existing partner data nodes. In addition, this will allow other data consumers to link eLTER services into their own web portals or workflows. Figure 2 provides an overview on the component architecture (in the following defined as cyberinfrastructure) focusing on the current and planned elements of the eLTER Information System. This consists of eLTER Catalogue services to document the digital and physical assets, the eLTER Data Repository services to storage and provide standardised access, the eLTER Visualisation services to visualise and access data assets, as well as the eLTER Analytical services providing a collaborative platform to develop analytical

pipelines and workflows. The eLTER Service Portal provides the end user interface to access the different services.

In addition, a range of web applications have been already developed to facilitate the scientific needs of the eLTER PLUS project. Table 1 provides an overview on eLTER services and workflows currently implemented in the eLTER DataLabs or provided as a package. This information is also related to Figure 2 and also relates to the specification of the different Thematic Service Areas (TSAs) of the forthcoming eLTER RI. The prototyped components show different technology readiness levels (TRLs) and are contributions to the different TSAs in the frame of data management. The information on related TSAs, where relevant, is given in the table below.

Figure 2. Overview on eLTER IT components and services (©Watkins)

Table 1. Overview on components and web applications available for the eLTER PLUS project

Component name	Description	Link	Contact
Digital Asset Register (DAR)	The Digital Asset Register (DAR) is a catalogue of all digital assets of the eLTER RI (e.g., datasets, models, analytical workflows) The DAR is a contribution to the TSA01_DM.02 Access to site data.	https://catalogue.ilter-europe.net/	Phil Trembath
DEIMS-SDR	DEIMS-SDR (Wohner et al., 2019, 2020) is a metadata editor and catalogue which allows users to create, publish and share information on research facilities, data collection activities, datasets and sensors. It provides its data to other components via standard interfaces (REST API, OGC CSW, OGC WMS/WFS) DEIMS-SDR is a contribution to the TSA01_DM.01 Site registration and cataloguing.	https://www.deims.org	Christoph Wohner

Component name	Description	Link	Contact
eLTER CDN	The eLTER Central Data Node (CDN) is the main storage area for eLTER's data assets. The CDN can manage different data formats such as geo-spatial data (geoserver), time-series (OGC-SOS) and unstructured data. The CDN is a contribution to TSA01_DM.03 Data ingestion and quality assurance.	https://cdn.lter-europe.net	Will Bolton
eLTER DIP	The eLTER DIP uses EcoSense as the visualisation platform implemented as a web GIS portal using JAVA (Angular - frontend and Spring - backend). It provides sites' metadata (from DEIMS-SDR), and RS and time series (OGC SOS) data from CDN. The eLTER DIP is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters using input information from DAR, CDN and DEIMS-SDR.	current address https://ecosense.biosense.rs	Vladan Minic
eLTER DataLabs	A virtual collaborative work space hosted in the cloud that allows users to access a range of environmental data, analytical methods, and assessment tools. The eLTER DataLabs is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters providing the underlying infrastructure to run analytical pipelines and workflows.	https://datalab.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk	Will Bolton
eLTER Vocabularies	The central vocabulary service of eLTER providing terms, term definitions, and term translations for EnvThes and the eLTER Controlled Lists.	http://vocabs.lter-europe.net/	Phil Trembath
ReLTER	ReLTER is an R package that provides access to DEIMS-SDR, allows interaction with software implemented by eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI), and improves the data/information shared by them.	https://github.com/ropensci/ReLTER https://github.com/oggioniale/ReLTER R	Alessandro Oggioni, Micha Silver, Paolo Tagliolato
deimsPy	deimsPy is a Python package that eases access to DEIMS-SDR.	https://pypi.org/project/deims/	Will Bolton / Christoph Wohner
PhenoApp	PhenoApp is a tool developed in Jupyter notebook which calculates and retrieves phenology metrics from EO images (Sentinel-2 and MODIS). It also allows downloading these metrics for eLTER sites and uploading in situ data with validation purposes. The eLTER PhenoApp is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.	Link not yet available	Diego García / Ricardo Díaz-Delgado
Cookie cutter	shiny App. This DataLab tool enables gridded and tabular data to be cut to the area of the LTER platform or LTER site. The Cookie cutter is a contribution to	https://github.com/eLTER-RI/spatial-data-processor	Will Bolton

Component name	Description	Link	Contact
	TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.		
ICOS/FLUXNET	Extraction and harmonisation of data from ICOS/FLUXNET based on the concept of the cookie-cutter. The app is a demonstrator for the functionalities. The eLTER ICOS/FLUXNET is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.	available through DataLabs	Will Bolton
DEIMSenrich	shiny App provides user interface to query and download data from deims.org using the DEIMS-SDR API. Extracted data can be linked to user defined data on eLTER facility level. DEIMSenrich in addition provides an overview on the sites selected. DEIMSenrich is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.	https://elter-enrich.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/	Ivo Offenthaler
CrocoTile	shiny App. This DataLab tool enables the identification of relevant Sentinel 1 and 2 tiles for a given eLTER site. The application was developed in the frame of the e-Shape project and adopted by eLTER. The CrocoTile tool is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.	https://elter-crocotile.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/	Ivo Offenthaler
Allosaur	shiny App. This DataLab tool enables the calculation of tree biomass with allometric functions. Input data are observations from a forest inventory survey. The Allosaur tool is a contribution to TSA01_DM.05 Site Information Clusters.	https://elter-treemasster.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/	Ivo Offenthaler & Johannes Kobler

The above-mentioned components of the intended eLTER Information System have been used to tag the workflows developed and identify relevant interlinks (see Chapter 3).

2.4 Data sources

eLTER observations are covering a wide range of characteristics of the ecosystem as well as the socio-ecological system focusing on the human-nature interactions. Peterseil et al. (2020b) provides a list of data types to be considered when designing the data workflows as well as the eLTER Information System. In addition, we also have to take into account a number of data origins or data sources, which have been identified in the process of defining the SOs and the related protocols. These could be roughly grouped into three groups for biotic and abiotic observations:

- *sensor-based* - automatic or human sensors are used to collect observations (e.g., chemical characteristics of soil water, profiles of nutrient concentration of standing waters, concentration of Chlorophyll a, ground heat flux)
- *sample-based* - methods or protocols are provided for the collection of a sample (e.g., water, sediment, ice, vegetation), the eventual transport to a laboratory, and observations are then made

on the sample, usually by sensor (e.g., SOHYD_170 "Profiles of nutrient concentration: NO₂, NH₄, DOC, DIC - standing waters")

- *retrieval-based* - data are collected or subsetted from existing data sources (e.g., land cover, population statistics) and harmonised and aggregated for the area of interest.

Additionally, *survey-based observations* focusing on questionnaires and interviews for socio-ecological research needs to be taken into account. Qualitative as well as quantitative information is collected on a sample of the population, e.g., stakeholders. Survey based observations are often subject to personal data and GDPR.

In addition, Koivula et al. (2022) describe digital assets to be considered in the development and design of the eLTER Information System, which is already extending the scope of the data sources to be considered. Here the following data sources are listed:

- *eLTER Standard Observation (SO)* data from the eLTER site network that has been standardised to comply with eLTER measurement protocols and methods, data formats and nomenclatures (e.g., code lists, vocabularies and ontologies). This includes data provided from the sites via the Virtual Access (VA) schema.
- *External data* (e.g., satellite data, observation data) that have been transformed to be compatible with other eLTER datasets. These data may not be re-shared as they are available from other third-party sources, but are maintained for efficiency and provenance of eLTER RI data workflows. Nevertheless, a data licence enabling reuse of the data via a shared licence (e.g., CC-BY) needs to be ensured.
- *Derived data products* that have been created through synthesis of different datasets and / or modelling of eLTER Standard Observations. This will include spatial interpolation of eLTER site data to form contiguous spatial coverages.

Nevertheless, both listings have their shortcomings when focusing on the data space to be addressed in the eLTER context. Therefore, within the scope of the current task, we tried to extend and specify the data sources and origins in a bit more detail. For this, specifications and examples provided by Halada et al. (2022), Peterseil et al. (2022), as well as by Zacharias et al. (2021), and the current discussion on the refinement of the SOs have been taken into account. Based on this, a number of additional data related requirements can be derived, which need to be taken into account

In the frame of eLTER we are focusing on the following data types to be handled by the different workflows. More details are given by Halada et al. (2022, D4.2) and Peterseil et al. (2022, D4.1):

Historic and legacy eLTER data (referred as non-SO-data)

- These are datasets observed by the different eLTER facilities and managed by them, but not consistently observed using the SO protocols and recommended methods. This could also include data observed in co-location with other RIs or research networks (e.g., ICOS). Data provision could be directly by the eLTER facilities or via related data portals (e.g., ICP Forests, ICOS, ICP Integrated Monitoring). This could include issues related to data policies applied according to the different procedures as well as applied data formats. In general, it can be assumed that a number of different methods and protocols are used and no common data format and standard is applied.
- These datasets are mainly covering biotic and abiotic observations and to a certain extent also socio-ecological and socio-economic data, if collected specifically at an eLTER facility. This can also include remote sensing data (e.g., drone flights, LIDAR scans), directly collected at or produced for a specific eLTER facility.
- These datasets can be (a) sensor based (including human observation) or (b) sample based.

- These historic and legacy data are relevant for the development of data products covering a long time range for a specific eLTER facility.

Requirements:

- All eLTER data assets need to be assigned to an eLTER facility by referencing the DEIMS.ID;
- Metadata on the datasets (and services) need to be available in machine-readable manner in order to enable their harvesting;
- Information on the method and protocol needs to be provided with the dataset in order to enable data integration, validation, and harmonisation;
- For sensor-based observations, metainformation on the sensor deployed needs to be provided in a machine-readable manner;
- For sample-based observations, metainformation on the sample needs to be provided.

eLTER SO data streams (referred as SO-data)

- These datasets are observed at the eLTER facilities according to the common and agreed SO protocols and recommended methods (base and prime⁴). According to the specification of the SO, common and harmonised data formats are applied and quality check routines can be applied.
- These datasets can be (a) sensor based or (b) sample based following a common data standard.
- In addition, quantitative and qualitative interviews (e.g., stakeholder configuration) can be performed.

Requirements:

- All eLTER data assets need to be assigned to an eLTER facility by referencing the DEIMS.ID;
- Metadata on the datasets (and services) need to be available in machine-readable manner in order to enable the harvesting of metadata and being referenced in the Digital Asset Register (DAR);
- Information on the SO method and protocol applied needs to be specified being the basic or prime method;
- For sensor-based observations, metainformation on the sensor deployed needs to be provided in a machine-readable manner;
- For sample-based observations, metainformation on the sample needs to be provided.

Currently, no data of this type is available as the SO protocols and methods will be implemented with the RI starting in 2025.

Third-party data (referred as non-eLTER-data)

- These datasets are data completing eLTER observations but not directly observed at the eLTER facilities (e.g., statistical information, data products from other networks repositories and citizen science data, Earth observation data products). Datasets are subsetted from existing data sources using a defined procedure (e.g., eLTER Cookie-Cutter⁵ (Halada et al., 2022)). These data sources

⁴ For the bulk of the Standard Observation variables, two types of methods are defined: (i) "prime", which represents methods according to the highest eLTER standard (in terms of accuracy, spatial and temporal resolution), and (ii) "basic", which represents a less elaborated methods (and in most cases more cost-efficient) combination of measurement method and protocol (derived from Zacharias et al., 2020).

⁵ see <https://github.com/eLTER-RI/spatial-data-processor>

and products are normally European, regional or national scale data products which are shared through the eLTER Information Cluster.

- Retrieval is either (a) on-demand (providing the services exist) or (b) pre-calculated (depending on the requirements and processing time needed).
- These datasets can be (a) part of the SO specifications or (b) additional data relevant for the scientific analysis.
- These datasets can reflect different kinds of data sources:
 - Official statistics on European or national scale (see Halada et al., 2022)
 - Derived Earth observation data products (e.g., land cover, phenology, biomass; see Silver et al., 2023)
- These datasets are retrieval based following a common data standard. In general, a common and agreed data format and standard compliant to the eLTER recommendations and requirements should be applied.

Requirements:

- If datasets are subsets for a specific eLTER facility, the data assets need to be assigned to a eLTER facility by referencing the DEIMS.ID;
- For retrieval-based data, metainformation on the data source and extraction procedure applied needs to be provided.

2.5 Logical data levels

Another aspect that needs to be taken into account when defining the data related workflows are the different logical data levels. The concept and use for eLTER is already defined in the project deliverables D11.2 (Koivula et al., 2022) and D10.2 (Peterseil et al., 2020b), but it needs to be revised to include not only SO data streams but also historic and legacy data from eLTER facilities (both variables relevant to SO data products and complementary datasets). When considering data stewardship in respect to data management, storage, and provision, these different levels are useful in defining the stages of quality assurance and data transformation workflows (Koivula et al., 2022). eLTER defines four logical data levels for the data and related data products that range from *raw data* (Level 0), *observation data* (Level 1), *cleaned data* (Level 2), to *derived data products* (Level 3) representing the processing status of the data and which are comparable with common practices from comparable RIs and research networks, e.g., ICOS (ICOS, 2022), TERENO (Kunkel & Sorg, 2016), or ACTRIS (ACTRIS, 2023). The logical data levels are defined based on the consideration for in-situ and remotely sensed observation data, but also apply for other data types (e.g., interviews or surveys). Data on all different logical levels need to be linked to metadata descriptions and provenance records in the eLTER DAR (Koivula et al., 2022).

Historic and legacy data from eLTER facilities not being observed based on the SO standard protocols and methods in general are considered as Level 0 data, as quality control and format is on the governance of the eLTER RI. Data quality assurance procedures are applied on eLTER facility level, but not necessarily complying to the eLTER requirements. Nevertheless, these data can be included into data workflows developing added-value higher level data products (Level 1 to 3) including centralised harmonisation and transformation. Metadata are required to enable the discovery through the central eLTER catalogue and to establish provenance chains for the implementation of higher level data products.

SO data (being in-situ sensor or sample based or remotely sensed) are collected according to SO standard protocols and methods, following clear definitions on quality control and formatting. These requirements are currently developed in the frame of defining the SO protocols and methods. In this respect, Level 1 data are raw observation data without undergoing any transformation. These data are included into data workflows developing added-value higher level data products (Level 1 to 3) including centralised quality control procedures, transformation and harmonisation.

For level 2 and 3 data products, data from historic and legacy data as well as SO data can include information on the accuracy (e.g., when combining data observed with different protocols and methods) and quality. This information needs to be part of the metadata description including provenance and linking to the processing pipelines.

2.6 Data reporting format

The eLTER Field Specification for Data Reporting (Peterseil & Geiger, 2020) is the starting point for a tentative harmonisation of the observation collected by eLTER facilities. It is inspired by data reporting recommendations from ICP Integrated Monitoring and ICP Forests, but also takes into account recommendations from GBIFs Darwin Core Extensions on sampling events. It is composed of both a documentation providing the description, and examples of eLTER data specification and template files for reporting data and metadata. The data reporting specification consists of different entities providing the data together with the necessary additional documentation (metadata) to ensure the use and re-use of the data and to enable flexibility and extensibility. The specification consists in the following entities:

- DATA - containing the observation values;
- STATION - containing information on the location of observation and sampling plots including the reference to the eLTER site;
- METHOD - containing descriptions of the variables and the methods and protocols applied;
- REFERENCE - containing information on code lists (e.g., taxon names, land cover type, soil type);
- EVENT - containing information on observation events (e.g., vegetation relevé, observation campaigns, sampling events), only provided if events or sampling campaigns are documented;
- SAMPLE - containing information on samples collected during a sampling event, only provided if samples are collected and stored and the information is provided with the data;
- LICENCE - providing information on the data licence applied and the usage restrictions.

Each data reporting has mandatory (M), conditional (C), and optional (O) metadata entries and the harmonisation of the data provided is assured by the use of a common structure.

In the frame of the current discussion on the SO protocol and method specification, the field specification might be subject to changes and clear definitions for the different SO considered. It is planned to publish the field specification as schema when these steps are done.

3 Identification of data workflows for eLTER RI and Science Cases

Johannes Peterseil, Alexandre Belleflamme & Hanna Koivula

The aim of task 10.2 was to identify and select data related workflows that are of relevance for the development of the eLTER Information System as well as for the development of data products to be shared within the emerging eLTER RI. All workflows addressed in the current work are related to the requirements of the eLTER PLUS project as outlined in the Description of Action of the Grant Agreement. In this respect, the RCs and the related Science Cases of WP8 and 9 but also the work on the Information Cluster done in WP4 were the main inputs for the work. We conducted a series of dedicated workshops and face-to-face meetings with the Science Cases to support them in the development of the workflows. In addition, we reviewed the deliverables of WP4 (Peterseil et al., 2022; Halada et al., 2022; Silver et al., 2023) to extract relevant workflows for the current work.

We also reviewed relevant RIs and research networks in the ecosystem and biodiversity domain to collect information on their workflows to get inspirations and recommendations for eLTER. This can never be extensive or complete and is used for a first indication. The information on the RIs and research networks is provided in Chapter [4.1](#) of the deliverable.

3.1 Modelling activities

In the frame of the current work, we modelled the data-related workflows as activity diagrams following basic UML and SysML notation for activities. Nevertheless, it is important to state that not a full SysML modelling procedure was applied. This needs to be achieved in the further development of the eLTER RI. The activity diagrams developed in the current task are an important input to the System Engineering work done in the eLTER enrich project, which aims to take a broader scope on all relevant workflows of the RI. Table 2 summarises the workflow elements used in the context of the work to model the activity diagrams.

Table 2. Workflow elements used to model the activities of the data workflows

Symbol	Description
	Start node for the activity of the workflow
	End node for the activity of the workflow
	Action or activity performed
	Object used in the workflow, e.g., data object
	Control flow between actions and/or objects
	Decision node
	Partition of the workflow, collecting, e.g., several actions conducted in one processing step
	Container for linked actions or activities, this can also reflect a component used in the workflow
	Data storage (of any kind), e.g., database or repository
	Data can be retrieved directly, e.g., as data service (e.g., OGC SOS, ftp download, https download)
	User
	Dedicated eLTER component (as indicated in Table 1)
	Document produced by an action

3.2 Workflow documentation

For each of the workflows, we provide a short description of the aim and specification. This information is summarised and shown in Table 3. This basic documentation is combined with the activity diagram and, if relevant, additional description of workflow steps. In addition, we aim to link the workflows to the user-defined epics collected through the ICT requirement collection process (Peterseil et al., 2020b).

Table 3. Basic documentation of the workflow

Workflow title/id	Short title or identification of the workflow
Aim of workflow	Short description of the aim and results of the workflow
Workflow description	Short textual description of the workflow and the main processing steps implemented
Input / data types / data level	Definition of the input data (type and level) to be used in the workflow
Output / data types / data level	Definition of the output data (type and level) to be produced by the workflow
Roles	User and roles involved in the workflow, basic users and roles are defined in Chapter 4.2
IT components	Reference to the main IT components of the eLTER Information System as indicated in Table 1. This also can include planned or future services and tools, as well as services and tools provided by third-party (e.g., EOSC)
Identification of objects (PID)	Specification of requirements for the persistent identification of objects (e.g., data) or actions (e.g., code) of the workflow
Metadata requirements	Specification of requirements for the documentation of specific elements (e.g., objects) of the workflow
GDPR and sensitivity	Short description, if relevant, on GDPR and sensitive data issues and how they should be addressed
EPIC	Link to the epics defined in the ICT requirement collection (Peterseil et al., 2020b)

Activity diagram (only an example) - in description of the activity diagrams of the workflows, a reference to the diagram.net file is given in the footnote, which can be accessed online. In the text of the deliverable, a copy of the diagram is included. Depending on the complexity of the diagram, there might be issues with the readability of the content. Figure 3 provides a dummy example of a workflow showing the use of the different elements to model the workflow.

Figure 3. Example dummy workflow showing the different elements of the activity diagram

4 Results

4.1 State of the art

Hanna Koivula, Alexandre Belleflamme, Alessandro Oggioni, Christoph Wohner & Johannes Peterseil

In order to develop the eLTER workflows, we surveyed a number of e-infrastructures, research infrastructures and research networks addressing the question on how other research infrastructures and observation networks design their data workflows concerning data submission, documentation, and sharing. In addition, we focused on relevant aspects like data acquisition and provision, quality control and assurance or persistent identification.

This entailed a multifaceted approach addressing the purpose of data sharing, the design of the data system, as well as the means of data provision. Understanding these variations in purpose and design is essential for eLTER to design and align its data workflows with the broader research landscape. Therefore, we group the surveyed research infrastructures and observation networks in the summarised description. More details are provided in Annex B (Chapter 9).

Distributed versus centralised

One important consideration for the design of the architecture and the related data workflows is the design of the data system. In general, a distributed design is implemented with differences in the level of data storage and maintenance. Whereas research infrastructures like the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) focus on the submission of raw data (which are in addition stored at the local sites) with a strong central component of the data management, observation networks like ICP Forest rely on the submission of aggregated data based on data calls. For the eLTER RI, a distributed design of the data system will most likely be applied. Depending on the eLTER Standard Observation, either raw data (mainly for sensor-based observations) or aggregated data will be ingested into the central data management system. In addition, eLTER will have to take into account historic observation

data which are not yet harmonised and integrated. Therefore, linking metadata through a central catalogue will be one of the major requirements.

Data Flows and Near-Real-Time (NRT) data

As defined in the eLTER Standard Observations, for many of the variables an automated continuous sensor-based data collection, often referred to as Near-Real-Time (NRT) data, is defined as prime method (e.g., soil moisture). Therefore, this is one of the important requirements for the future implementation of the Research Infrastructure. European scale Research Infrastructures such as the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS), or the Terrestrial Environmental Observatories Network (TERENO, Germany) at the national scale, implemented continuous data collection and provision to cope with the requirement of Near-Real-Time data provision and input to continuous modelling efforts as part of Copernicus services (e.g., Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS)⁶). Data flows are implemented with a minimum delay applying a two-level quality procedure on the level of the data collection facility and centrally on the level of the central management and storage. In case of ICOS, e.g., EUDAT services like B2SAFE are used as well as handle PIDs for identification of intermediary data elements. Data are ingested into higher level data products (Level 2 to 3) issuing a DataCite DOI for persistent identification.

In addition, in-situ data are collected, e.g., based on annual data submission calls, adhering to defined data reporting formats. Here, services and tools are provided, e.g., ACTRIS in-situ data⁷, to check and validate structure, format and content of the submitted data contributions. Here also a two-level data quality control is applied with a first level and basic control on the level of the data provider before submission and a second level on the central services before ingestion. In the frame of eLTER, this is especially relevant for survey- and sample-based observations with longer intervals.

Data submission and sharing

Conversely, monitoring networks operating under the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (LRTAP) convention, such as the International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests (ICP Forest), International Cooperative Programme on Integrated Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Ecosystems (ICP Integrated Monitoring), and the International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of the effects of Air Pollution on Rivers and Lakes (ICP Waters), adhere to harmonised protocols and dedicated data calls using predefined reporting formats for data submission. Data quality control is done on the level of the single observation sites as well as the re-structuring and aggregation of data according to the data specification for the different sub-programmes. Raw data are managed on the level of the individual observation sites with their original temporal and spatial resolution and in many cases only aggregated information is submitted to the program centre (e.g., on monthly resolution). Central quality control is applied on the submitted data before ingesting it into the central database. In general, this level of data (e.g., monthly resolution) is provided and shared as data products with the community following the individual data sharing and use policies of the observation networks. Higher level data products are not provided. For many of the eLTER facilities co-located with observation activities for the International Co-operative Programmes under the UN LRTAP Convention, this is a well-known and established procedure. This experience and expertise could be used for the eLTER RI for selected eLTER Standard Observations or historic data.

⁶ see <https://insitu.copernicus.eu/news/how-in-situ-data-brings-air-quality-and-greenhouse-gas-emissions-into-focus>

⁷ see e.g., <https://ebas-submit.nilu.no/>

From data to products

As an example for a topical data network, we investigated FLUXNET, which is a global network integrating eddy covariance data from different networks (including ICOS) and site PIs (Pastorello et al., 2020). These contributions originate from regional networks and are periodically amalgamated and standardised into FLUXNET data product releases. FLUXNET provides clear specifications and central second level quality control procedures. FLUXNET is organised by regional networks (e.g., AmeriFLUX, ICOS) fostering and facilitating a continuous and up-to-date stream of submitted data. Approaches and governance in developing data products from FLUXNET should be taken into account when designing eLTER data products (e.g., soil moisture).

Global Data Aggregators

Biodiversity data aggregators play an important role in harmonising ecological knowledge. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) stands as a global data aggregator, offering fundamental vocabularies and structures that facilitate the sharing of biodiversity information. GBIF not only provides tools for data aggregation and sharing but also champions clear standards such as Darwin Core (DwC) and Ecological Metadata Language (EML). The harmonisation of terms for various purposes and data products ensures the seamless integration of biodiversity information. GBIF additionally supports the research community with clear semantics and tools for the effective management of biodiversity data, encompassing both data collection and aggregation.

Securing personal data

Navigating the legal and ethical dimensions of data management is paramount. In this regard, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) emerges as a key player. CESSDA's commitment to GDPR-compliant provision and sharing of information sets a high standard. Collaborating with CESSDA affords eLTER insights into dealing with GDPR regulations and implementing advanced Metadata (MD) catalogues for unstructured data. This advanced approach not only ensures data privacy but also streamlines data access and sharing within the bounds of legal and ethical frameworks.

Additional data sources

The integration of citizen science initiatives, including iNaturalist, eBird, and Zooniverse, introduces an additional dimension to eLTER's data landscape. These initiatives contribute additional insights to eLTER sites, either through direct participation or as sources of valuable information retrieval. Efforts to harmonise the structure of citizen science data are ongoing, underpinned by standardised processes and observations. A noteworthy feature is the active involvement of users, exemplified by platforms like iNaturalist and eBird, where the quality of observations undergoes continuous improvement, often involving peer review processes. This commitment to data quality extends to structuring information about the quality of data, a practice that not only enhances data reliability but also promotes transparency. Citizen science initiatives provide indispensable tools to support harmonised data collection, including methods to better comprehend data biases, improve accuracy, and adapt the focus of data collection.

Incorporating citizen science into eLTER workflows is a step to be considered. Nevertheless, these initiatives could serve as valuable sources of additional information, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of ecological dynamics. Currently, this aspect is not addressed in the workflows so far.

Services and tools

In addition, e-infrastructures like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) or LifeWatch ERIC do not only provide input to the definition of workflows, but also provide a range of services which could be used to implement the workflows in the last phase of the project. This will be further assessed and elaborated in cooperation with WP 11 or the eLTER PLUS project dealing with the ICT service piloting and dissemination of data products.

More details on the surveyed research infrastructures and observation networks are given in Annex B (Chapter 9) of this report.

4.2 Actors and roles

Based on the draft Data Management Plan for the eLTER PLUS project (see Peterseil et al., 2020a; Watkins et al., 2020), a number of actors have been defined as having a major role in the eLTER RI and the related data workflows. In order to comply with the development of the workflows, we adapted it to the current needs.

The following groups were identified as relevant actors in this use cases:

- **Data collector and provider** - actors running the current observations at the eLTER facilities and providing raw observation data. This can also include the deployment and basic maintenance of sensors.
 - Site and Platform Coordinators (SPC) – are the site managers or data providers running the long-term monitoring and providing long-term in-situ data for the eLTER network and RI.
 - Site Principal Investigators (SPI) - are the main investigators at the eLTER facilities implementing the observations, recommendations, and requirements of the eLTER SO standard protocols and methods.
- **Data curator** - actors running and coordinating the process of creating, organising, and maintaining datasets to enable usability and accessibility (e.g., ensure consistency of metadata). This can be, depending on the organisation level of the eLTER facility, related to the scientific personnel or done by dedicated local data managers. Data curation is addressed on three different levels
 - local scale on the level of the eLTER facility
 - national scale on the level of the national LTER network or eLTER National Research Infrastructure (NRI)
 - RI scale on the level of the European eLTER RI related to the relevant Topic Centres (e.g., data management)
- **Data user and consumer** - main actors using and accessing datasets and data products for the eLTER RI and the eLTER project. For the eLTER PLUS project, this encompasses the
 - Research Challenge (RC) leads – leading the Research Challenges “Biodiversity loss”, “Biogeochemical control of ecosystem functions”, “Climate-Water-Food nexus”, and “Socio-Ecological systems” and coordinating the Science Cases across the work packages. This includes also the WP leaders for WP8 and WP9.
 - Science Case leads and contributors – leading and conducting the Science Cases in the context of WP8 and WP9 reflecting the science community. They define the data and ICT

requirements and they are the main users of the data provided in the eLTER Information System by the eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms.

- **Data centre and repository** - main actors for the management and storage of the main eLTER data repository (eLTER Central Data Node) and providing the main facilities for cataloguing and discovery. Data management and provision is addressed on three different levels
 - local scale on the level of the eLTER facility
 - national scale on the level of the national LTER network or eLTER National Research Infrastructure (NRI)
 - RI scale on the level of the European eLTER RI related to the relevant Topic Centres (e.g., data management)
- **eLTER Data Management Coordination** – main actors coordinating and planning the development of the architecture, services, and tools.
- **eLTER Data Management Support and Maintenance** – team providing and prototyping the IT services for the project (e.g., staging area, eLTER CDN, DEIMS-SDR, B2SHARE, eLTER DIP, EnvThes, eLTER Data Lab).

In addition, to ensure knowledge exchange and capacity building, a team supporting the experts at the eLTER facilities and data providers in the data collection, management as well as performing a basic quality control and harmonisation of the data, is needed. The team needs to be supported by the Science Cases and RCs.

4.3 Workflow steps

Hanna Koivula

Workflows and methods for capturing critical requirements for workflow tools with a data management plan (DMP) have been identified and processed in earlier deliverables. Milestone M10.2 focused on the identification of key data workflows implemented by the case studies as input to the planning and implementation of task 10.2 on prototyping selected workflows. Based on the collected ICT and Data Requirements (D10.2, Peterseil et al., 2020b), a questionnaire was sent to the Research Challenge leads and Science Case contributors to collect information on the intended workflows. The questionnaire covered questions about the data used in the analysis and working steps to be applied within the eLTER infrastructure and outside. It also included a question on the intended data product to be shared in the eLTER context.

The results were used to identify and prioritise requirements from the different Research Challenges in relation to the overall eLTER data lifecycle. It is important to acknowledge the special requirements of each Research Challenge and to ensure that the future RI provides access to such services that ensure interoperability and usability or fitness-for-purpose of any data collected by the site (not only SOs). However, equally important are the phases or steps in the workflow, which did not gain many votes in the survey. Lack of votes may indicate that these features (e.g., metadata creation or Data Citation with PIDs) need to be embedded to the tools so that the data provider does not need to search separate services for these workflow steps. Agile development methods will help further prioritisation and ensure implementing all of the essential requirements in suitable order, making sure the entire data lifecycle is functional as the features will be added and the so-called skeleton RI will mature to its full potential.

The workflows in this deliverable will concentrate on the eLTER RIs internal workflows, and here we handle all incoming data as Level 0 - raw data even if it can be validated data from and for some other

RI. As indicated earlier, a typical scientific data workflow involves the following generic stages: 1) Data collection, 2) Data processing and management, 3) Temporal and spatial harmonisation and aggregation, 4) Gap filling and data fusion, 5) Data documentation and provenance, 6) Data publication and citation, and 7) Data Visualisation and Analysis.

Here follows a short description of each phase in eLTER RI context:

1) Data collection

Data acquisition and methods documentation involves the collection of data from various sources, such as experiments, surveys, or simulations. The raw data may be in different formats, such as text, images, or numerical values from sensors, and in addition each method may need to be described/documented with metadata to ensure reproducibility of the process.

Data retrieval and ingestion happens from a service or an API to the eLTER RI information system. Once data at a local source/site is collected and formed into digital record (raw data), it will be ingested into the eLTER RI information system. In business architectures, data ingestion means the process of importing large, assorted data files from multiple sources into a single, cloud-based storage medium—a data warehouse, data mart, or database—where it can be accessed and analysed. Data transfer utilises standards that preserve the structure (syntax) of the data and may also include controlled vocabularies from the source.

2) Data processing and management

As data may be in multiple different forms and come from numerous sources (using different standards and vocabularies), before **merging** the data into a federated service, it needs to be sanitised and transformed into a uniform format. This transformation process is called Extract/Transform/Load (ETL) process and it can be processed with tools at the source information system or if the data are retrieved to a federated system in a so-called “staging area” (DAMA International, Henderson & Earley, 2017). In the eLTER RI, this means retrieving data from the sites (legacy, experiment, or SO data) and **processing** it into eLTER data products (Level 1 to 3). A master copy of the raw data must always be curated and maintained in the site owner institutions own data systems or alternatively in EUDAT B2DROP and B2SHARE sharing and publishing platforms and ingestion to eLTER information system retrieves raw data from the local services or APIs. Also, third-party data (products) can be retrieved from APIs and ingested to eLTER workflows for forming eLTER data products.

Data management may happen locally at the site and there may be parts of the process documentation that do not need to be ingested, even if they are essential to be available at the source in case validity of the record needs to be checked. Here, the data management means eLTER RIs data management or processing phase, which is needed for making data interoperable in the eLTER context and hence allows for merging or compiling data from multiple sources.

After being ingested to the eLTER information system, data harmonisation and enriching, i.e., processing will take place. All data processing steps should be documented (logged) to enable capturing of the data lineage and provenance.

Variable harmonisation starts with data formats checking to enable technical merging of multiple variables from different data sources. Semantic interoperability is achieved by asserting or annotation of variables with chosen vocabularies to ensure unambiguous expression of variables. As the data are coming from different sites and possibly different kinds of sensors or processes, originally used expressions represent the raw data and any changes, mappings, or annotations must be documented and the original expressions in the raw data should be citable at the source or archived as-is in the eLTER system. Semantic interoperability is especially important for

biodiversity and sociological data, where the data are often interpretations from the collected evidence, i.e., unstructured data.

For biodiversity data, the most important quality assurance step is to harmonise the species names by mapping the species names or checklist to the platforms backbone taxonomy facility (e.g., GBIF - <https://doi.org/10.15468/39omej>, PESI - <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.3.e5848>, WoRMS). In addition to species names harmonisation, also data collection methods and possible monitoring protocols are essential for comparing or merging datasets from different locations. Different methods to collect biodiversity data are used. Therefore, preserving the structure of a dataset requires much information about the context, which is most often expressed with Darwin Core community standard (DwC) and its extensions and by using Ecological Metadata Language (EML) as metadata. Both community standards allow expressing variables with externally maintained semantic artefacts (vocabularies or ontologies), which enable mapping and merging different data together without losing the semantic meanings of the data entities.

Socio-ecological data can hold both quantitative and qualitative data, and transforming the raw data, i.e., “evidence” into a numeric format to be analysed is called coding. Quantitative coding is the process of categorising the collected non-numerical information into groups and assigning the numerical codes to these groups. In qualitative research, coding simply means: “how you define what the data you are analysing are about” (Gibbs, 2007). Coding is a process of identifying a passage in the text or other data items (photograph, image), searching and identifying concepts and finding relations between them. Therefore, coding is not just labelling; it is linking data to the research idea and back to other data. The codes, which are applied, enable organising data so they can be examined and analysed in a structured way, e.g., by examining relationships between codes (CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide⁸)

In addition to the unstructured data described above, all ecological research also needs direct measurements or modelled scenarios from the natural environment. The **variables and units** that come as direct measurements from sensors are structured data, and when merging this data from multiple sources, semantic interoperability is equally important (compared to interpreted unstructured data). In the eLTER context, the **EnvThes Vocabulary** service and the **Digital Asset Register (DAR)** will allow unit transformation or annotating variables and hence searching data born from different kinds of measuring processes (sensors, laboratory analyses, remote sensing, etc.) by using unambiguous expressions.

Data Quality is not an absolute measure, but dependent on the purpose (or repurpose) of data collecting and use. Maintaining high data quality often involves trade-offs. For example, aiming for very high accuracy or granularity can increase the cost and time required for data collection, potentially at the expense of data completeness or timeliness. In the case of very data intensive research, the cost of selecting and archiving raw data is also a major constraint. The future eLTER RI needs to carefully consider these trade-offs in the context of their specific goals and constraints.

The New European Interoperability Framework (EIF)⁹ suggests that high-quality data should meet the user's needs in terms of *accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, accessibility, compliance, and understandability*. It also emphasises the importance of data management practices that support these principles, such as data governance, data stewardship, and data quality management.

⁸ see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3820473>

⁹ see https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

Each RC should adopt guidelines for the domain specific data management practices and document the original data quality by using suitable vocabularies or by creating their own data dictionary, when necessary, to be able to maintain consistent data quality through time. The RCs define the core requirements and quality measures for each SO, but still the raw data should be stored as rich as possible in the original format and use mappings and crosswalks rather than transform the original data into new formats for merging data into one interoperable data source. The essential components in the data quality and verification are the (commonly agreed) community standards and semantic artefacts (vocabularies and ontologies) that are used to express data structure (syntax) and keeping the semantic expressions unambiguous between different data sources when data is transferred.

Sensitivity is tightly related to data quality and it needs to be acknowledged already in the planning step of the eLTER workflow(s). Sensitive data is defined as any information that is protected against unwarranted disclosure. Protection of data may be required for legal or ethical reasons, for issues pertaining to personal privacy, or for proprietary considerations. Sensitive data includes: human data (e.g., health, genetic and personal information, data that may identify a person), ecological data (e.g., location of endangered species or other conservation efforts), confidential data (e.g., trade secrets), and data that is otherwise deemed sensitive. The FAIR principles have been introduced to ensure that data “is as open as possible but as restricted as necessary” and the principles also require the licensing and restrictions to be machine actionable, which makes partial restrictions and visualisation of sensitive data possible at a suitable level of granularity or anonymisation. However, anonymisation is not a straightforward process and it requires careful consideration of various factors, which need to be incorporated in the eLTER RI’s data policies and architecture principles. This includes establishing roles and responsibilities for data management, setting policies for data quality and metadata, and defining procedures for data access, sharing, and archiving. Also sometimes, it may be necessary to de-anonymize the data, for example, to validate the results or to handle data errors. In such cases, a secure mechanism may be needed to retain this capability, such as the use of pseudonyms that can be mapped back to the original identifiers.

Especially in socio-ecological research, where data can be collected through surveys, it is crucial to understand when and how data constitutes a personal data file and what the implications are of collecting data covered by the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The design stage (filling and maintaining a DMP) is particularly important for this type of data, as interviews require a contract with the interviewees and a statement of how and where the data will be used. While each participating organisation will primarily have its own local data policies, eLTER RI should also develop and publish policies and guidelines to ensure that the data available are also legally interoperable. Data anonymisation, pseudonymisation and de-anonymisation techniques, methods, and tools should also be part of any services and training provided by the future eLTER RI. Also, secure data processing platform(s), where the anonymisation process can be executed, is needed. When possible, readily available solutions like EUDAT B2SAFE should be evaluated.

- 3) Temporal and spatial harmonisation and aggregation** are steps in the workflow to aggregate input datasets to a common spatial and temporal resolution. This is especially true when integrating different data sources (e.g., historic and legacy datasets) into higher level data products. Tools (such as GIS software, Python, R, SQL [with spatial component] etc.) enable temporal and spatial aggregation and harmonisation. This is done using, e.g., simple temporal aggregation scripts to calculate annual means or sums. Spatial aggregation is, e.g., addressing the calculation and upscaling from plot scale to forest stand scale (e.g., calculation of forest biomass). A number of scripts and tools can be applied and the proper documentation and reference as part of the provenance documentation is needed.

- 4) Gap filling and data fusion (part of actual analysis and visualisation)** covers the steps of the workflow that allow the generation of data products derived from eLTER site data, which are continuous in time and possibly also in space. Gap filling can rely on statistical interpolation methods, such as Fourier transform, linear or polynomial interpolation, etc., to obtain continuous time series, and bilinear interpolation, triangulation, kriging, etc. to produce continuous data fields in space. Gap filling can also be achieved with conceptual models, where the original data are used for calibration and validation, and with mechanistic models, where the original data are ingested, e.g., through data assimilation. These gap filling methods might require additional data (e.g., contextual data, proxy data, forcing data), which might come from different sources (third-party data) and need to be combined through data fusion. These additional datasets then also need to undergo the processing steps explained above. The gap filling method as well as the additional datasets, which have been possibly used, must be detailed in the metadata record of the newly generated data product.
- 5) Data documentation and provenance** is a record that describes data products and, importantly, their origins and processing histories. The Digital Asset Register provides tools to document and describe data products. It consequently offers potential data users with a means to find relevant data and to make an assessment of their appropriateness. Provenance information provides transparency about data's origins and any processing methods it has undergone and so helps potential users determine a data object's quality and validity. It allows us to describe how different data products are related to each other. For example, how a level 3 data product that has been gap-filled has been derived from level 0 raw data. The Digital Asset Register will aim to make such connections visible and traceable allowing users to navigate between data objects in a provenance chain and ascertain the processes and pipelines by which the data objects were generated. This will support researchers in answering questions such as: What were the assumptions on which the data are derived? Under what conditions are they valid? What other data objects were derived from the same sources?
- 6) Data publication and citation** involves publishing the data and the results of the analysis with metadata descriptions and archiving the original raw data as well as the processed data products along with the documentation in a repository or database for future use. In the eLTER RI this repository is the Central Data Node (CDN). Data products and their workflow documentation should be reproducible, e.g., the raw data and processes leading to the data product should be transparent and citable with a PID. This would also enable tracking data usage and gaining credit to the data publisher (institution and/or researcher).
- 7) Data visualisation and analysis** steps in the workflow cover tools and services that are essential for access of data and data products and also visualising the data statistics before the actual analysis. The process needs to include providing access to metadata about **methods and protocols** and the observation design. Visualisation is addressing spatial data as well as time series information for an area of interest (e.g., sensor, plot, eLTER facility) also depending on the type of variable or data to be displayed (e.g., time series of temperature needs different representation than wind speed and direction).

4.4 eLTER Workflows

Based on the interaction with the Science Cases and the evaluation of the deliverables of the eLTER PLUS project we identified a number of data related workflows. These encompass (a) the acquisition and access to historic and legacy data from eLTER facilities, (b) the access and extraction of relevant EO information, (c) the access and extraction of relevant third-party data, (d) the prototyping of data products for eLTER, and (e) the provision of SO conformant data to the central eLTER facilities. All workflows are described following a basic schema and are modelled with a generic activity diagram.

All the eLTER workflow diagrams are stored in a GitHub repository¹⁰. The diagrams thus collected can be edited (see Annex C, Chapter 10) and the different versions can be found again.

4.4.1 Acquisition and access to legacy and third-party data

The provision of historic and legacy data as well as other third-party data sources is an important component of building the eLTER Information Clusters and providing quality-controlled data for the scientific workflows. We analysed the material collected in the frame of the project (see Peterseil et al., 2022; Halada et al., 2022; Silver et al., 2023) and extended the scope to additional relevant workflows. The following chapter summarises the main workflows identified.

4.4.1.1 Harvesting metadata from eLTER node data portals (Digital Asset Registry - DAR)

Will Bolton, Holger Villwock & Johannes Peterseil

Workflows title/id	Harvesting metadata on eLTER datasets and services from national eLTER Data Node (DN)
Aim of workflow	<p>The DAR is being developed as the central repository of digital assets of the RI, which includes datasets. Many national (and subnational) networks already host datasets in online catalogues, whose records should be available in the DAR while linking back to the original source.</p> <p>The harvesting workflow has been successfully tested with the SITES metadata portal (https://data.fieldsites.se/portal/) and will be extended to other metadata catalogues such as B2SHARE.</p>
Workflow description	<p>The SITES workflow is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • once a week, check the SITES data portal sitemap (XML) for the current list of records • for each record (JSON-LD) in the list of type “Dataset”: • if it has previously been imported, update it to reflect any changes • if it has not previously been imported, create it • save import metadata (handle.net ID and modification time) to the record <p>All records in the SITES portal have a handle.net persistent identifier which is used to match records in the SITES catalogue with records in the DAR.</p>
Input / data types / data level	Metadata on biotic or abiotic observation datasets or services (e.g., OGC SOS, OGC SensorThing, OGC WMS/WFS) (Level 0)
Output /data types / data level	Registered metadata on biotic or abiotic observation datasets or services (e.g., OGC SOS, OGC SensorThing, OGC WMS/WFS) (Level 0) in the Digital Asset Register (DAR)
Roles	Data provider
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local metadata catalogue • Digital Asset Register (DAR)
Identification of objects (PID)	Data objects and metadata needs to be identified by a persistent URI or PID); direct harvesting of DataCite metadata is done via DataCite DOI

¹⁰ <https://github.com/eLTER-RI/eLTER-workflow-diagrams>

Metadata requirements	In addition to the metadata provided by the local catalogue, information on the SO (eLTER vocabulary) and the linked eLTER facility (DEIMS.ID) needs to be provided. This is either read from the dataset metadata or needs to be annotated manually by the data provider reviewing the metadata record in the DAR.
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant for biotic and abiotic
EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects • EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data objects • EPIC 2.2 Harvesting of metadata on data objects

Activity diagram¹¹

Figure 4: Schematic workflow harvesting metadata from national eLTER Data Node (DN) into the DAR

¹¹ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1z0O86n_AabQ7A_oc0PnECn7gBhSfzJUP/view?usp=sharing

4.4.1.2 Mobilising historic and legacy eLTER data

Johannes Peterseil & Ulf Mallast

Workflows title/id	Register historic and legacy eLTER data (Level 0) in the Digital Asset Register (DAR)
Aim of workflow	Mobilising historic and legacy observation data from eLTER facilities is one of the aims of the eLTER RI and network. The workflow describes the provision of a single dataset or service to be registered in the central eLTER data catalogue, the Digital Asset Register (DAR). These data objects are locally curated and quality controlled historic eLTER data and can encompass any biotic or abiotic datasets and services of relevance for the eLTER RI and network. In general, the datasets and services provide data for a SO that have not been observed using the basic or prime method as defined by the SO protocols and methods. Quality control and data format transformation is applied on the local level before sharing the data with the wider scientific community.
Workflow description	A single dataset or a range of datasets is selected to be catalogued in the central eLTER data catalogue. Harvesting of the metadata by the DAR is done based on DataCite DOI and accompanying metadata or by the URI provided (machine readable metadata is a requirement). If datasets or services are available online, the metadata record is registered in the DAR. If reference to the SO as well as to the eLTER facility is not provided within the metadata, this information needs to be manually annotated by the data provider using the DAR. If datasets are not available online (e.g., only internal data provision in a database, which is not accessible for external users), the datasets need to be transformed using the eLTER Data Specification and shared via a trusted and persistent repository also issuing a DataCite DOI and providing rich metadata descriptions, e.g., B2SHARE, Zenodo, Pangea. Dataset metadata are then harvested by the DAR using the DataCite DOI and DataCite metadata schema. The workflow ends when the metadata are registered in the DAR and the dataset is findable via the eLTER central data catalogue.
Input / data types / data level	Metadata on biotic or abiotic observation datasets or services (e.g., OGC SOS, OGC SensorThing, OGC WMS/WFS) (Level 0)
Output /data types / data level	Registered metadata on biotic or abiotic observation datasets or services (e.g., OGC SOS, OGC SensorThing, OGC WMS/WFS) (Level 0) in the Digital Asset Register (DAR)
Roles	Data provider
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local metadata catalogue ● Digital Asset Register (DAR) ● trusted and persistent data storage component (criteria: DOI issuing, e.g., B2SHARE, Zenodo, Pangea)
Identification of objects (PID)	Data objects and metadata needs to be identified by a persistent URI or PID); direct harvesting of DataCite metadata is done via DataCite DOI
Metadata requirements	In addition to the metadata provided by the local catalogue, information on the SO (eLTER vocabulary) and the linked eLTER facility (DEIMS.ID) needs to

	be provided. This is either read from the dataset metadata or needs to be annotated manually by the data provider reviewing the metadata record in the DAR.
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant for biotic and abiotic
EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects ● EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data objects ● EPIC 2.2 Harvesting of metadata on data objects

Activity diagram¹²

Figure 5: Schematic workflow providing and registering selected datasets in the central eLTER Data Catalogue (DAR)

¹² see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ntYzZM0XS6mSLJarl18S7_ irrzXo8d91/view?usp=sharing

4.4.1.3 Mobilising historic and legacy eLTER facility data shared via Third-Party data portals (Use Case Fluxnet and ICOS, D4.1)

Will Bolton & Johannes Peterseil

Workflows title/id	Extraction of eLTER facility data based on third-party data portal
Aim of workflow	Ecosystem research on hydrological and biogeochemical processes of ecosystems strongly relies on measurements of <i>in-situ</i> gas flux data, e.g., to quantify the effect of water deficits on ecosystem functions and health. The need to validate complex ecosystem models increases the importance of easy access, assessment, and download of harmonised datasets of multiple observation networks (e.g., FLUXNET and ICOS) that can currently just be accessed individually. Aiming for this, we developed a prototype demonstrator for gas flux data from such networks and stations corresponding to eLTER or provided by co-located eLTER sites.
Workflow description	The workflow ingests metadata and selected variables from the gasflux networks for a chosen eLTER Site, visualises them and offers a direct data download in the eLTER data format (Peterseil & Geiger, 2020). The user selects an eLTER facility of interest to retrieve and harmonise the data. Assignment of the eLTER facility to the FLUXNET or ICOS sites is done by information provided in DEIMS-SDR and/or analysis of the geolocation based on the site boundaries provided. Data are transformed from the FLUXNET data format to the eLTER Data Specification for direct data use. Currently, no re-sharing of the resulting datasets is implemented. As part of the workflow, a basic provenance pointing out the source and manipulation of the dataset is provided. The workflow is implemented in the eLTER DataLabs using R-Shiny as end user interface. No authentication is needed. We tested some capabilities, which can be upgraded for the implementation of the Information Clusters. The use case and workflows are described in more detail in the deliverable D4.1 (Peterseil et al., 2022). For the time being, the workflow was implemented using downloads of the selected base datasets.
Input / data types / data level	Quality controlled and harmonised gasflux data products from ICOS and FLUXNET <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FLUXNET 2015 dataset (Pastorello et al., 2020)¹³ ● Drought 2018 dataset provided by ICOS (Drought 2018 Team, and ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre., 2020)¹⁴ If ingested into an eLTER data product workflow, these data are considered as level 0.
Output /data types / data level	structural harmonised datasets following the eLTER Data specification. After transformation, data are considered as level 1
Roles	Data user
IT components	eLTER DataLabs (through ShinyApp), DEIMS-SDR API
Identification of objects	Currently not considered, as these are preliminary and transformed datasets

¹³ see <https://fluxnet.org/data/fluxnet2015-dataset/>

¹⁴ see <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-products/YVR0-4898>

(PID)	which are not republished. If they are ingested in a data product, the resulting data product will be DOI-ed and referenced to the input sources as part of the provenance chain.
Metadata requirements	Provenance of the extraction pipeline is recorded in the provenance metadata. This needs to be passed with the data and ingested, if higher level data products are generated.
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant
EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EPIC 3.1 Quality control and data manipulation (format transformation) ● EPIC 3.2 Provenance tracking ● EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER data product (Level 0)

Activity diagram¹⁵

Figure 6: Demonstrator workflow to retrieve and harmonise FLUXNET / ICOS data using the eLTER DataLabs

¹⁵ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1V_JnNulu0c9nT6m2SpR4Y81HVJAeIFkS/view?usp=sharing

4.4.2 Mobilising relevant Earth Observation data in the frame of the eLTER Information Cluster (D4.3)

adapted from Micha Silver & Carmela Marangi (Silver et al., 2023)

Workflows title/id	Mobilising relevant Earth Observation data in the frame of the eLTER Information Cluster
Aim of workflow	The workflow aims to provide relevant EO data products for the area of an eLTER facility. The input data layers have to be cropped to the boundary of the eLTER sites or platforms, to make the information available for successive integration in research activities at the site scale. This includes cropping as well as pre-processing to contribute to the formation of an information cluster and to overcome the issues related to different native time and space resolutions of multiple data layers.
Workflow description	<p>The starting point of the analysis carried out in WP4 has been the identification of simple variables of common interest, i.e., whose use is recurrent in many research activities performed at the eLTER sites. Examples are Land Cover, NDVI, Digital Elevation Models. Part of these variables have well known sources of known quality offering also some processing tools.</p> <p>As a result of this preliminary analysis, three simple variables have been selected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land Surface Temperature (LST at 1000 m spatial resolution and 8-day temporal resolution); • NDVI / EVI (NDVI and EVI at 250 m spatial resolution and 16-day temporal resolution) • Land cover (Landcover from CORINE for the years 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018) <p>The EO data was prepared and uploaded to the CEH DataLabs infrastructure. This included code in the R programming environment and data covering the above sample eLTER sites. Datasets of both NDVI and Land Surface Temperature (LST) were acquired from the NASA MODIS satellite covering the decade from 2010 - 2020. Plots of average NDVI and average LST for each site were prepared. In addition, code was prepared to clip the CORINE land cover data to the boundary of each site. Both the resulting cropped datasets and the code to prepare this data were all uploaded to DataLabs for use by the community (Silver et al., 2023).</p> <p>Data are used on-demand (implemented) or can be ingested in the eLTER Central Data Node for later access (to be implemented).</p>
Input / data types / data level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • site boundaries of the eLTER facilities (provided by the DEIMS-API) • Land Surface Temperature (LST at 1000 m spatial resolution and 8-day temporal resolution); • NDVI / EVI (NDVI and EVI at 250 m spatial resolution and 16-day temporal resolution) • Land cover (Landcover from CORINE for the years 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018)
Output /data types / data level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cropped EO data products for the eLTER facility or interest

Roles	Data user
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● eLTER DataLabs ● DEIMS-SDR API ● eLTER Digital Asset Register ● eLTER Central Data Node ● eLTER Vocabularies
Identification of objects (PID)	<p>If cropped datasets are stored in the eLTER Central Data Node, a DOI will be issued.</p> <p>If cropped datasets are used on-demand, no DOI will be issued and reference to the original datasets is provided as part of the provenance.</p>
Metadata requirements	Provision of the provenance information (data source and processing steps) as part of the metadata is needed.
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant
EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects (if stored in the CDN) ● EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data object (if stored in the CDN) ● EPIC 3.2 Provenance tracking ● EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER data products

Activity diagram¹⁶

Figure 7. Dynamic retrieval of EO data products from large scale data source for a selected set of eLTER facilities

4.4.3 Identification and extraction of Third-Party data source for Information Cluster

Johannes Peterseil

Workflows title/id	Identification and extraction of third-party data
Aim of workflow	The retrieval of complementary data sources supporting the eLTER data frame is beneficial to eLTER and aids building the site information clusters. This addresses the identification of relevant data sources and portals (activity diagram A, Figure 8) and access and extraction of data for a selected eLTER facility (activity diagram B, Figure 9). This is relevant (a) to get additional data for data analysis or visualisation, (b) to retrieve data

¹⁶ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/19F6zwnz1oQIMWcVfMI3cfo_75Ai3I9t/view?usp=sharing

	<p>from eLTER sites provided through national level catalogues, or (c) to retrieve data from eLTER sites provided to other sister RIs (e.g., ICOS) or monitoring networks (e.g., ICP) (see Peterseil et al., 2022). The workflow is also valid for the extraction of statistical information (see Halada et al., 2022).</p> <p>This workflow applies to (a) long-term observation data provided from other data sources than eLTER covering biotic and abiotic data, and (b) retrieving data from official statistics (socio-economic data)</p>
Workflow description	<p>First, in the Identification of data source, the thematic scope for data source screening is defined, e.g., by the eLTER SOs as well as the specific data requirements resulting from research questions to be addressed. Nevertheless, the thematic scope might change and be extended in future based on additional needs of the eLTER RI as well as the LTER network. The thematic scope is the filter for selecting relevant input data sources. This results in a list of relevant data sources being subject to the further assessment steps.</p> <p>The Data Source Assessment (assess) includes two sub-components. The first sub-component 'Assessment Coverage' focuses on the fitness-for-purpose addressing the thematic, spatial, and temporal coverage of the data source of interest. Currently, we do this step manually by screening and assessing relevant data sources using information provided by the metadata, websites, and personal communication. If the 'fitness-for-purpose' fails, the data source is not considered as relevant. The second sub-component 'Assessment Structure' focuses on selected elements of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) dealing with the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and re-usability. In the current context, we focused on elements like: (a) data format and standard supported, (b) data access mechanisms, (c) metadata formats and standards supported, (d) metadata access mechanisms, and (e) data licence. In addition, in future procedures also data citation (e.g., availability of persistent identification for static and dynamic datasets) as well as semantic references should be taken into account. If a data source is not accessible by either direct machine-to-machine interaction (e.g., API), personal contact or download, the data source is not considered as relevant (taken from Peterseil et al., 2022).</p>
Input / data types / data level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● relevant third-party data sources ● accessible datasets and services
Output /data types / data level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● documentation of data sources and portals ● cropped datasets following the eLTER Data Specification (observation and statistical data) (Level 0)
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● eLTER Data Management ● Data provider ● Data user and consumer
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● eLTER DataLabs (e.g., cookie-cutter) ● eLTER Central Data Node ● eLTER Digital Asset Register ● eLTER Vocabulary Service ● ReLTER, deimsPy and relevant packages

Identification of objects (PID)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> in case the data are stored in the Central Data Node (as part of the Information Cluster), persistent identification is needed. The issue of re-publishing data or data extracts needs to be clarified with the input data source (if already published via DOI) in case of on-demand extraction (no permanent storage), no persistent identifier is issued
Metadata requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> documentation of the third-party data source with basic information on scope, data usage and licence, as well as access options and conditions documentation of the extracted dataset (including provenance and processing pipelines)
GDPR and sensitivity	not relevant
EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data objects EPIC 3.1 Quality control and data manipulation EPIC 3.2 Provenance tracking

Activity diagram A - Identification and documentation of third-party data source¹⁷

Figure 8. General workflow to identify third-party data sources relevant for the eLTER Information Cluster (Silver et al., 2023 after Peterseil et al., 2022)

¹⁷ see <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QFTXJUErjcf-USOuEFg9o-RArrQI-VcC/view?usp=sharing>

Activity diagram B - Identification, extraction and documentation of third-party data source¹⁸

Figure 9. Generic workflow retrieving in-situ legacy data. Boxes in orange reflect the respective components of the eLTER Information System (Peterseil et al., 2022)

¹⁸ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qiK56UOikt_1lhGmRxzCBxrVwbB2381G/view?usp=sharing

4.4.4 Provision of geo-spatial data for eLTER facility

Christoph Wohner & Johannes Peterseil

Workflows title/id	Provision and publication of geo-spatial data
Aim of workflow	Storing and publishing geo-spatial data resulting from eLTER facilities (e.g., habitat maps, EO data products calculated for the area of interest) using the Central Data Node capabilities.
Workflow description	<p>Potential workflow for standardised geodata products (see Fig. XX) (A)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sites provide geodata based on data specification as defined by eLTER, e.g., geopackage file with particular column names and data types • Files are stored in a defined storage location according to defined naming conventions consisting of, e.g., DEIMS.ID, SO id, time range • Data is imported into a geodatabase (potentially there are separate geodatabases for the different data products) • Data in database is shared using standardised geodata services such as WMS and WFS • Metadata is generated automatically based on information linked to the data product, e.g., author, data licence, method description, etc. <p>Potential workflow for unstandardised geodata (B)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data file is stored and described in persistent data storage, e.g., in B2Share under LTER • The DAR automatically fetches metadata from B2Share and creates a record • File-based access is ensured but service-based access is not available
Input / data types / data level	<p>For workflow for the provision of geodata, a broad distinction can be made between:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised geodata products that are based on SOs (A) • Less standardised geodata products probably collected in the scope of research projects (B)
Output /data types / data level	Geo-spatial data provided as OGC WMS/WFS
Roles	Data provider
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eLTER Central Data Node • eLTER Digital Asset Register • eLTER Vocabulary Service
Identification of objects (PID)	Persistent identification of data layers by the eLTER Central Data Node
Metadata requirements	Documentation of the data layer (including provenance and processing pipelines)
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant

EPIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects • EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data objects • EPIC 3.1 Quality control and data manipulation • EPIC 3.2 Provenance tracking
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Activity diagram¹⁹

Figure 10. Potential data flow for standardised geodata

4.4.5 Prototypical data products (Science Cases)

As part of the eLTER PLUS project, Science Cases have been implemented to prototype and show the capabilities of the eLTER network and data. These have been organised along four research challenges covering (a) Biodiversity loss (BDL), (b) Biogeochemical processes (BGC), (c) Climate-Water-Food Nexus (CWF), and (d) Socio-Ecological Systems (SES). In addition to the scientific questions addressed, in cooperation with WP11 and WP10, the Science Cases worked on the harmonisation and integration of datasets that can be seen as prototypes for the development of eLTER data products. In the following sections, we provide a summary of the workflows implemented. More details are given in the specific Science Case reports in Annex A (Chapter 8).

¹⁹ see <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hljHYIMeTpXzm2GpgXBe4vZd6z-lePRj/view?usp=sharing>

4.4.5.1 Biodiversity loss

Hanna Koivula, Alessandro Oggioni & Johannes Peterseil

Workflows title/id	Integrating and harmonising biodiversity observation data to enable analysis of biotic heterogeneity and biodiversity changes
Aim of workflow	Biodiversity data, together with other observational data from the environment, is needed for studying the mechanisms behind the biodiversity loss phenomenon. The workflow aims to create a data product harmonising and integrating biodiversity observation time series (covering different organism groups) to enable the analysis and modelling of biodiversity trends.
Workflow description	Identify and specify needed data objects from multiple sources/repositories (e.g., GBIF, iNaturalist, OBOE) to be enriched and harmonised and finally merged into a data product. This also includes the semantic harmonisation and the taxonomic harmonisation of the input data sources as well as removal of redundant species information (if, e.g., a data source was already compiled). In addition, the dataset can be extended by traits information.
Input / data types / level	Heterogeneous observational data, and its documentation (metadata of all objects) (Level 0)
Output /data types / level	Harmonised and enriched data product (Level 1)
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data provider • Data user (generation of a data product) • eLTER Data Management Team
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUDAT B2DROP • eLTER Central Data Node • eLTER Digital Asset Register • eLTER Data Labs • R/RStudio
identification of objects	Dataset metadata, Observational data, Event information, Check-list (used in the original data), other semantic artefacts (used to express measurements of facts)
Metadata requirements	EML and DwC and extensions (for data transfer)
GDPR and sensitivity	Biodiversity data sensitivity is mostly related to locality information of endangered species
EPIC	EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER data products

Activity diagram²⁰

eLTER Workflow: Generic workflow to integrate and harmonise biodiversity observation data based on the science case inputs

Figure 11. Generic workflow to integrate and harmonise biodiversity observation data for eLTER

²⁰ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1XmK9SO5rZ6_jk8aC9SPdDXW8xKjGILe5/view?usp=sharing

4.4.5.2 Biogeochemistry processes

Lauren Gillespie, Eugenio Diaz-Pines & Thomas Dirnböck

Workflows title/id	Synthesising bio-geochemical data to analyse ecosystem processes
Aim of workflow	<p>The eLTER PLUS Task 8.2 aims to increase process understanding of the impact of climate change and extreme weather events on carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling and feedbacks in a broad range of ecosystems. To this purpose, data on C and N fluxes were analysed. Further, extreme weather events (i.e., droughts) were characterised. It was the goal of the task to facilitate a) identification of critical environmental thresholds and tipping points in C and N turnover and fluxes across the eLTER spectrum of ecosystems, climate zones, and socio-ecological contexts and b) improvement of our understanding of the impact of extreme weather events and climate change on ecosystem processes.</p> <p>Further details on the workflow are given in Chapter 8.4</p>
Workflow description	Data from a range of eLTER facilities were ingested and harmonised following the eLTER Data Specification. It included quality control and outlier detection as well as gap-filling for soil moisture data.
Input / data types / data level	observation data from eLTER facilities and third-party data sources (e.g., ICP Forest) (Level 0)
Output /data types / data level	harmonised (data structure, temporal, spatial), integrated and basic quality-controlled observation data for eLTER facilities (Level 1)
Roles	Data user (production of data product)
IT components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● R/RStudio ● eLTER Data Lab ● eLTER Digital Asset Register ● eLTER Central Data Node
Identification of objects (PID)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● persistent identification of the resulting added value data product (DOI or handle) within the Central Data Node ● persistent identification and publication of the code generating the data product
Metadata requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● documentation of the data product including provenance (input data and data manipulation pipeline) ● documentation of the code generating the data product
GDPR and sensitivity	Not relevant
EPIC	EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER Data Products

Activity diagram²¹

Figure 12. Workflow on integrating soil moisture, soil temperature and soil respiration

²¹ see <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18VMNt3sO0GL56UagXsOBT3TjP-KTDhLn/view?usp=sharing>

4.4.5.3 Climate-Water-Food nexus

Christian Poppe, Nikolaos Nikolaidis & Alexandre Belleflamme

The scope of the Climate-Water-Food nexus Science Case is to establish a workflow and to demonstrate how site data, e.g., from eLTER but also possibly from other RIs, as well as third-party data (e.g., remote sensing data) can be integrated into numerical models (as forcing data or via data assimilation techniques) or used as calibration and validation of these models to answer scientific questions about ecosystem functioning and services. In particular, tasks 8.3 and 9.3 aim to analyse the response and resilience of ecosystems to drought events at the site and catchment scale and on the pan-European scale, respectively.

Workflows title/id	Multi-source data processing for modelling
Aim of workflow	The aim of the workflow is to retrieve and identify data from multiple sources, to process and combine them so that they can be ingested by models to produce high level, synthesised data products.
Workflow description	Once the data needs for one model have been identified, the required data are retrieved, possibly from multiple sources. If the data are not already harmonised (i.e., quality checked, gap filled, with consistent units, etc.), they undergo a harmonisation process including steps like unit conversion (to the units needed by the model) and time aggregation (to the input time step of the model). Then, a gap filling procedure is applied, e.g., for time series through interpolation, or on the basis of available proxy variables. This step might require the retrieval of additional data, which have to undergo the same process. The obtained preprocessed data are then quality controlled (e.g., by time aggregation for checking mean values, statistics; by visual inspection; by comparison with reference datasets and the literature). Note that these steps can be skipped if the data are already available as harmonised, quality-controlled data products. Finally, the data are stored and formatted to the requirements of the model (e.g., file and data format). The compiled dataset can then be ingested by the model to produce, after some postprocessing (e.g., synthesis, time aggregation, unit conversion, data and file formatting), high level data products.
Input / data types / level	Raw or already processed (harmonised) data products from sites (eLTER, other RIs), from remote sensing, from other models (e.g., reanalysed atmospheric forcing) - data levels 0-3
Output /data types / level	new high level, synthesised data products, continuous in time, at site, catchment, ... pan-European scale - data level 3
Roles	data user, modeller
Supporting components	DEIMS-SDR, CDN, EcoSense, Data Labs, HPC System
PID (if relevant)	Required for the resulting level 3 data product
Metadata connections	All processing steps, in particular transformation (units), aggregation (in time and/or space), gap filling, model name and version should be included in the metadata of the final data product.
GDPR relevance	Not relevant
EPIC	EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER Data Products

Activity diagram²²

Figure 13. Prototype workflow for the Climate-Water-Food Nexus integrating data from multiple sources as modelling input

²² see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dTo65CCO1Qju8gstlINPq4tqA_kDBWC_/view?usp=sharing

4.4.5.4 Socio-ecological systems

Veronika Gaube & Bastian Bertsch-Hörmann

The socio-ecological Science Case (Task 8.4) addresses the analysis of local-to-regional land-use actors and other relevant stakeholders of the local land-use system. Analysis aims at identification of key stakeholder groups and the qualitative description of their positions within the socio-ecological system. Special emphasis is put on their perceptions of and vulnerability to major environmental problems, climate change impacts and risks, as well as the implementation of actual/potential adaptation measures. A second focus is set on the land-use related communication between stakeholder groups, detailing the connections between land users and their communication partners. The analysis contributes to a holistic system-understanding necessary for the implementation of a land-use Agent Based Model (ABM) with a focus on climate change adaptation, land-use decision making and social learning. The research design is based on a mixed-method approach using qualitative semi-structured expert interviews and content analysis, as well as a quantitative online survey and social network analysis.

Still the activity diagram related to this Science Case needs to be developed and is not included in the current deliverable. The respective section in Annex A provides detailed information on the requirements and the related workflows. Please refer to Chapter 8.8 in Annex A.

4.4.6 Draft data workflow for Standard Observations (SOs)

Johannes Peterseil & Alessandro Oggioni

For the eLTER Standard Observations basically four different data sources can be identified (see Chapter 2.4). These encompass (a) sensor-based observations, (b) sample-based observations, (c) retrieval-based observations, and (d) survey-based observations. As the SO protocols and methods are currently still under development, we focused on a generic workflow addressing sensor and sample-based observations. Retrieval based observations are focusing on existing third-party data and are covered by the workflow on Identification and extraction of third-party data and the workflow Mobilising relevant Earth Observation Data (see Chapter 4.4). The workflow on survey-based observation collecting data, e.g., on stakeholder configuration and attitudes still needs to be developed and will be addressed in task 10.3 as further discussion is needed.

Workflows title/id	Provision and publishing data from Standard Observations
Aim of workflow	The workflow aims to ingest and quality control Standard Observation data collected on defined protocols and methods into the central data storage facility. It covers the process from data submission to generation of the Level 1 data product with harmonised data on eLTER facility level.
Workflow description	Data are acquired and first quality controlled on the level of the local monitoring station. The data are stored locally and are provided to the central services either by file-based submission (defined format based on eLTER Data Specification) or sensor-based (e.g., OGC SOS, SensorThing API). The data are reflected as Level 0 data with basic level of quality control (e.g., range tests or outlier detection based on the requirements for the SO protocol and method). Data resolution and formatting is defined by the SO protocol. Metadata and identification is needed also on Level 0 in order to enable provenance tracking for the later processing steps. Level 0 data needs to be referenced in the Digital Asset Register. Submitted data are ingested in the

	<p>staging area and checked, if a resubmission of data was done. If yes, a version history is created and managed by the Digital Asset Register. Data are centrally checked for data format, semantics (e.g., variable naming, units, species names) as well as central data quality check is performed based on the criteria defined by the SO protocol and method. If the dataset passes the checks, the data are ingested into the central data storage and flagged as Level 1 data and the metadata and provenance chain is created. For Level 1 data a DOI is issued and published as citable data product.</p> <p>In addition, if relevant, metadata on the sensors, the samples and the observation location needs to be provided in advance in order to enable the linking of the data to these entities.</p> <p>For the central quality check routines, a sufficient environment (e.g., eLTER Data Labs) needs to be provided.</p>
Input / data types / level	observation data (Level 0) based on eLTER SO protocols and methods
Output /data types / level	cleaned data (Level 1) quality controlled and harmonised based on SO protocols and methods
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data provider and local Data Manager ● eLTER Data Management Team ● eLTER Quality Assurance Group
Supporting components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local data management system (data provision) ● eLTER Central Data Node (data storage and identification) ● eLTER Digital Asset Register (metadating and provenance) ● DEIMS-SDR (site reference) ● eLTER Data Labs (scripting)
PID (if relevant)	<p>Raw and observation data (Level 0) are managed and stored by the local eLTER facility. For referencing in the provenance chain persistent identification and versioning of this data level is suggested. This could be done, similar to the ICOS data workflow, with handle PID to allow proper referencing in the provenance chain.</p> <p>Higher level data products, e.g., Level 1, needs to be shared and identified using a DataCite DOI to allow citation of the data product.</p>
Metadata connections	<p>All data levels need to be documented and referenced with metadata using the Digital Asset Register. This is also true for the Observation data (Level 0) which can be generated automatically as data submission (either near-real-time or based on frequencies) is repeated. This metadata also needs to include the provenance on data manipulations and quality checks, including software and scripts if relevant.</p> <p>In addition, metadata on the sensor (still need to be defined where) and the sample (if relevant, still need to be defined where) need to be provided for the dataset. Reference to the Observation location (documented in DEIMS-SDR) needs to be provided to define the spatial scope of the observation.</p>
GDPR relevance	<p>For biotic and abiotic observations not relevant.</p> <p>For survey-based observations, GDPR and securing personal data needs to be considered. This will be addressed by task 10.3 focusing on the SES data product on stakeholder configuration and attitudes.</p>

<p>EPIC</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EPIC 1 Ingest and upload data objects ● EPIC 2.1 Creation of metadata on data objects ● EPIC 3.1 Quality control and data manipulation ● EPIC 3.2 Provenance tracking ● EPIC 5 Creation of eLTER Data Products
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For higher level data products (Level 2 and 3), first workflows are drafted in Prototype data products. This workflow will further be developed in the frame of task 10.3 and are therefore not included in the generic SO workflow.

Activity diagram²³

Figure 14. Generic data flow for SO data from the local monitoring station to the central facilities (staging and publishing area)

²³ see https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dfSZwKxReU7djh_vJSzY0Y2qUpmgTc1/view?usp=sharing

5 Conclusions

The aim of task 10.2 was to analyse requirements and develop draft workflows together with relevant stakeholders within the eLTER PLUS project as the basis for the development of prototype eLTER Data Products. The work done has to be seen as a continuous process with the activity diagrams and descriptions of the workflows as living documents. The work was done on the interface between the scientific components of the project, represented by the WPs 3, 4, 8 and 9, and the IT component of the project, represented by WP 11.

Based on the interaction with the Science Cases and the evaluation of the deliverables of the eLTER PLUS project, we identified a number of data related workflows. These encompass (a) the acquisition and access to historic and legacy data from eLTER facilities, (b) the access and extraction of relevant EO information, (c) the access and extraction of relevant third-party data, (d) the prototyping of data products for eLTER, and (e) the provision of SO conformant data to the central eLTER facilities. Further work on the development of the eLTER Standard Data Products (SDP) has already started and will be continued in the final phase of the project. Close interaction is needed, especially on the interface to the development of the SO protocols and methods, which are currently under development. Further input on the data format requirement and detailed data specification (e.g., resolution, sensors) will provide further input in the final phase.

A subject, which needs to be addressed both on the governance level as well as on the technical level, is the contribution of data from eLTER facilities to co-located RIs and research networks. In order to avoid re-submission or re-publication of data, clear guidelines and rules need to be defined. This could not be addressed in the full detail as required in the current phase, as additional input from the definition of the SO protocols and methods is needed. With the development of detailed workflows for the prototype eLTER Data Products, this issue has to be addressed in more detail. In addition, further efforts in defining standards and vocabularies is needed. This is not a one-time task, but an ongoing process that needs to be managed and governed throughout the enterprise's lifecycle. Therefore, many organisations establish data governance programs or structures (like a data governance council or a chief data officer role) to oversee this work and ensure that standards and vocabularies evolve in line with the enterprise's changing needs and goals.

Nevertheless, the current work provides an overview on the data related workflows to be addressed by the eLTER Information System and the eLTER data governance. In the Enterprise Architecture (EA) method, the architecture principles guide the design and evolution of the infrastructure to ensure that it effectively meets its objectives and provides value to its users. By establishing clear architecture principles and agreeing on the commonly used standards (standards portfolio) and semantic artefacts (vocabularies and ontologies), research infrastructures like the eLTER RI can provide a reliable, efficient, and user-friendly environment that enables high-quality research and fosters scientific innovation. These principles also provide a benchmark against which the infrastructure's design and performance can be evaluated and improved over time.

Architecture principles and standards portfolio and FAIR implementation profile are useful tools for defining how the Level 0 raw data will be processed into Level 3 data products. The content and level of detail of the DMP template needs to be updated as part of infrastructure development and maintenance. Taking advantage of machine actionable DMP tools (maDMP) can enable automation of workflows and remarkably help to achieve higher FAIR maturity, which requires machine actionable data "elements" (such as methods descriptions, workflows or other data/process documentation) (Hettne et al., 2023). The future eLTER RI DMP tool should support the entire eLTER workflow, and if made machine actionable, it could help automation of the workflows.

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8 Annex A - Science Case workflows

This Annex provides a detailed description of the different Science Case contributions focusing on the transformation, integration, and harmonisation of historic, legacy and third-party data to address the research questions raised by the eLTER PLUS project. This is seen as the first trials of defining and developing data products and to extract relevant workflow steps. Updated versions of the scripts and workflows will be available via GitHub in future²⁴.

Examples for the different RCs, namely Biodiversity loss (BDL), Biogeochemical processes (BGC), Climate-Water-Food Nexus (CWF), as well as Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) are provided.

8.1 Biodiversity loss (BDL) - Compilation of species information

Martin Musche

8.1.1 Scope

One aim within task 9.1 is to investigate long term changes in the composition of plant communities across eLTER sites. Specifically, we examine whether there have been temporal changes in β -diversity. Using the hierarchical partitioning approach by Tatsumi et al. (2021) and the temporal β -diversity index of Legendre (2019) we investigate patterns of population differentiation across space and time and relate these changes to site characteristics, changes in environmental conditions and species traits.

8.1.2 Workflow

8.1.2.1 Vegetation data

Data retrieval

Vegetation data from permanent plots were obtained from different sources:

- eLTER plus data collection (B2DROP folders)
- eLTER H2020 data collection (public datasets in B2SHARE)
- Data collected from eLTER site managers by Pilotto et al. (2020). The dataset was provided by Peter Haase for internal purposes.

It emerged that different sources can contain the same datasets. However, these datasets often differ in their temporal extent and level of processing. Therefore, data were checked manually for duplicates and the most recent versions were used for subsequent analyses. No data were queried from databases. Rather, file-based datasets were downloaded from the respective repositories or handed over by collaborators.

Data format harmonisation and transformation

First, data formats were harmonised to allow the data to be automatically read into the analysis software. For this purpose a new template was created. It consisted of the eLTER plus data collection template which was complemented by new columns to capture additional information not covered by the original template. Then, datasets were transformed according to template structure. For this purpose R scripts were used. Due to unique properties of each dataset individual R-scripts had to be

²⁴ <https://github.com/eLTER-RI>

applied. In cases of low standardisation data had to be transformed manually. Depending on the properties of the respective dataset the transformation included the following main steps:

- Joining taxon data, event data, spatial data and species reference lists
- Rearranging the order of columns
- Renaming of column names
- Adding content (e.g., variable names)
- Reshaping from wide to long format

For some datasets (e.g., ICP Forests, UK-ECN network) the link between network-specific site identifiers and DEIMS.IDs had to be established.

Variable harmonisation

Datasets differed regarding spatial reference systems, time formats and taxonomic reference systems. Geographic projections were harmonised using the R package *sf* (Pebesma 2018) and times were harmonised using the R package *lubridate* (Spinu 2017). Species names were harmonised using the GBIF backbone taxonomy. For this purpose, an internally developed R-script was applied. Misspellings and other inconclusive species names were checked manually and assigned to proper names if possible.

Quality control and outlier detection

Obvious errors, e.g., letters in columns where only numbers should occur, were identified and excluded.

Data fusion

Once the site-based data files were in the correct shape and harmonised they were merged using a R-script.

Unit transformation

Units were not transformed because for the purpose of this Science Case only species presence data are required. However, for further applications abundance data need to be harmonised. This includes the harmonisation of scales for species cover (percentage, Braun-Blanquet, Fadenhauer) and the coding system of vegetation layers.

Spatial aggregation and harmonisation

For the present Science Case species lists were aggregated over subplots within sites.

Temporal aggregation and harmonisation

Vegetation time series from eLTER have been collected in different time intervals ranging from 1 to 10 years, as well as in irregular time intervals. Therefore, species presence data were aggregated into new time intervals ranging from 6 to 12 years, depending on the question. Large time intervals have the advantage that only few sites need to be excluded from temporal analyses, but at the expense of temporal resolution.

Gap filling

No approaches to fill gaps in the data were applied.

Data documentation

The documentation of data manipulations mainly took place within R- scripts.

8.1.2.2 Site data

Site specific data not contained in the vegetation dataset, e.g., central coordinates and habitat data, were retrieved from DEIMS-SDR. These data were later merged with the output from the analyses explaining patterns of β -diversity change.

8.1.2.3 Climate data

Gridded climate data were obtained from the E-OBS climate dataset of the Copernicus Climate Service. Depending on the variable yearly means, sums, minimum or maximum values for eLTER sites were extracted. Mean values of these climate variables were calculated for the respective time periods under study. These were used to explain patterns of β -diversity change over time.

8.1.2.4 Trait data

Data retrieval

Trait data were obtained from different sources such as the TRY database (Kattge et al. 2019).

Variable harmonisation

Species names were harmonised using the GBIF backbone taxonomy as described above

Figure 15. Workflow to prepare data for biodiversity analysis.

8.1.3 References

Kattge J, Bönsch, G., ..., Wirth C (2019) TRY plant trait data base. enhanced coverage and open access. *Global Change Biology* 26, 119-188.

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Tatsumi S, Iritani R, Cadotte MW (2021) Temporal changes in spatial variation: partitioning the extinction and colonisation components of beta diversity. *Ecology Letters* 24, 1063-1072.

8.2 Biodiversity loss (BDL) - Stream invertebrates

James Sinclair & Peter Haase

8.2.1 Scope

Among others, task 9.1 aims to quantify spatial and long-term changes in the biodiversity and composition of stream invertebrate communities at the European scale. To do so, we collated data on communities from different European countries and ecoregions and then characterised spatiotemporal changes in biodiversity (e.g., abundance and taxon richness), the relative abundance of different taxa, and functional traits (e.g., feeding guilds). Our goal was to determine whether these riverine communities were generally improving or degrading through time and to compare these changes among different ecoregions.

8.2.2 Workflow

8.2.2.1 Taxon data

1) Data retrieval

The macroinvertebrate time series data was assembled from a data call in 2020 to eLTER site as well as European ecologists and environmental managers in general. Each time series has a minimum of eight years of data, with data collected from the same season (defined as any three consecutive months) and following the same methods within sites.

2) Data trimming

The dataset contains time series ranging from 1970 to 2020, however the majority of the data is available from 1992 to 2019. Data from outside these years may therefore need to be removed prior to analyses to avoid any biases that may occur owing to low sample sizes in certain years. Additionally, if the analyses are intended to be compliant with the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), then the time series for certain countries may need to be truncated to ensure they comply with accepted WFD methodology. For example, collection methods in Germany changed after 2000 to comply with the WFD so data from prior years may need to be removed.

3) Data harmonisation

The taxon names were harmonised across the dataset as of August 2021 using the taxa list from www.freshwaterecology.info (FWE). This process was performed by generating a list of all unique taxon names, verifying these names using the 'Taxon Validation Tool' and matching each taxon to its unique AQEM code, then correcting any names that cannot be verified. However, all taxa should still be checked prior to any analyses for relevance to the study system and in case some names may have changed through time. Any taxa names that cannot be found in FWE can be updated using other databases, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database.

The level to which a given taxon is identified may also need to be harmonised, but the amount of harmonisation required can vary by country. For example, some countries have the same level of identification through time for all taxa, whereas others may identify a taxon to different levels, such as the species-level in some years and to the genus-level in others. Data users may choose to keep the original data if these issues have little effect on the resulting analyses or may choose to harmonise the identifications by raising all affected taxa to the highest level of identification.

Table 4. Example of a biodiversity dataset showing the number of individuals of different species observed on a yearly basis at a given site

sample_id	site	country	year	month	lat	long	GAMMARUS DUEBENI	GAMMARUS LACUSTRIS	GAMMARUS PULEX	GAMMARUS ZADDACHI	GAMMARUS SP.
107000001_24.04.1999	107000001	denmark	1999	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	8
107000001_03.04.2000	107000001	denmark	2000	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	50
107000001_26.03.2001	107000001	denmark	2001	3	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	17
107000001_24.04.2002	107000001	denmark	2002	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	18
107000001_28.04.2003	107000001	denmark	2003	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	35
107000001_22.04.2004	107000001	denmark	2004	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	67	0	0
107000001_15.04.2005	107000001	denmark	2005	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	31	0	0
107000001_28.04.2006	107000001	denmark	2006	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	34	0	0
107000001_24.04.2007	107000001	denmark	2007	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	128	0	0
107000001_03.04.2008	107000001	denmark	2008	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	276	0	0
107000001_01.04.2009	107000001	denmark	2009	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	75	0	0
107000001_01.03.2010	107000001	denmark	2010	3	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	32	0	0
107000001_28.04.2011	107000001	denmark	2011	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	22	0	0
107000001_29.03.2012	107000001	denmark	2012	3	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	35	0	0
107000001_29.04.2013	107000001	denmark	2013	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	7	0	0
107000001_28.04.2014	107000001	denmark	2014	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	8	0	0
107000001_08.04.2015	107000001	denmark	2015	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	5	0	0
107000001_21.04.2016	107000001	denmark	2016	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	4	0	0
107000001_18.04.2018	107000001	denmark	2018	4	57.47237	10.48534	0	0	0	0	0

In this example, site 107000001 has two identified Gammarus taxa from 1999 through 2018 (Table 4). Gammarus sp. are reported up to 2003 with Gammarus pulex thereafter. There are a variety of reasons why a shift from genus-level to species-level taxa may occur, including changes through time in the dominant life stages (e.g., switching from juveniles to adults) or changes in taxonomists. Data users may choose to keep the original data if these issues have little effect on the resulting analyses or may choose to harmonise the identifications. In this example, harmonisation could be performed by switching all Gammarus pulex to Gammarus sp. to have a consistent level of identification across years, or it could be assumed that all Gammarus sp. are likely Gammarus pulex given that no other Gammarids have been recorded at this site. This harmonisation process should be repeated for all taxa in countries that exhibit these types of issues.

4) Data standardisation and transformation

Stream invertebrates are sampled following similar protocols in each country, but the collection and identification methods can differ within each resulting in differences in the range of values and units used for taxon abundances. The data must therefore be first standardised and/or transformed because the raw values cannot be directly compared across all countries. These changes depend on the intended analyses. For example, if the number of taxa (i.e., richness) need to be compared, then richness can be calculated for each site and then transformed to z-scores (centred to the mean and divided by the standard deviation) across sites within each country. Alternatively, if compositional

analyses is the goal, then the levels of taxon identification would have to be first harmonised across the involved countries (see #3) and then converted to a form that would not use raw abundances, such as relative abundance-type transformations. If temporal analyses are the goal, then another option is to use slopes of change through time instead of the annual values.

8.2.2.2 Trait data

1) Data retrieval

Trait data for European macroinvertebrates are available from FWE. A unique list of all taxon names must first be generated and then verified using the 'Taxon Validation Tool'. Once any necessary corrections have been made then the desired traits can be selected and downloaded for each taxon following validation.

2) Gap filling

We use a two-step approach to fill in missing trait data. First, if the trait data for a given taxon was unavailable, then we checked whether data was available from the next highest identification level. For example, if species-level data was missing then we checked for genus-level data and if that was missing we used family-level data. Second, if no trait data could be found then we averaged trait values across all taxa at the lowest level of identification available. For example, if no data was available for a given species at the genus- or family-levels, then we used the average trait values across all species within the genus to produce a genus-level trait value. Note that medians may provide more accurate values compared to averages if trait data is available for many taxa.

3) Data standardisation and transformation

The trait values from FWE are fuzzy-coded and traits from different sources can have different values. For example, some individual trait modalities (the subcategories traits can be divided into, such as shredder/grazer/etc. for the feeding trait) have scores ranging from 0 to 3 and the total sum of the scores can differ across taxa. Others can use a different scoring system, such as binary (0/1), or can use a scoring system that always sums to the same total for each taxon, such as scoring modalities from 0 to 10 but the total score always sums to 10. Consequently, if the traits come from different scoring systems, then the values must be standardised by converting to proportions. To do so, the taxon value for a given modality is divided by the total sum of all modality values for the respective trait. For example, a taxon with trait modality values of 3, 3, 0 would be transformed to 0.5, 0.5, 0 (i.e., equal affinities for both the first and second modalities). Note that this conversion will mask some differences among taxa within certain traits. For example, values of 3, 3, 0 would have the same proportions as 2, 2, 0 despite differences in their raw values.

Figure 16. Workflow to prepare the macroinvertebrate taxa and trait data for analysis.

8.2.3 References

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8.3 Biodiversity loss (BDL) - Biodiversity trends

Rita Bastos, Ângela Lomba and Joana Vicente (CIBIO, BIOPOLIS)

8.3.1 Scope

WORKFLOW of data analysis for the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK' (eLTER Plus task 8.1) - contribution to WP10.

8.3.2 Workflow

This report describes the working steps of the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the eLTER site of Moor House', using a list of prioritised workflow elements:

1) Data retrieval (access to data, e.g., API)

The biodiversity dataset used in this study includes vegetation sampling (plant species list and relative abundance) obtained from Pilloto et al. (Provided by Martin Musche in June 2022). Abiotic datasets include in-situ abiotic measurements of soil chemistry and meteorological data obtained from ECN (downloaded from http://data.ecn.ac.uk/request_form.asp in June 2022) (See 12A).

2) Data format harmonisation and transformation (including check of data formats)

All datasets (Biodiversity and Abiotic) have been received as csv files (See 12A).

3) Variable harmonisation (semantic) as the basis for further check of the data

Plant species names in the original dataset were harmonised via data cleaning and abbreviation procedures (See 12B).

4) Quality control and outlier detection (variable / site level and across site / variable level - tipping points and change point detection / are site data comparable)

Samples in which the quality of the data have been affected during sampling were removed from the database (See 12B).

5) Data fusion

Not applicable

6) Unit transformation

Vegetation raw data (plant species list and abundance data) was transformed into biodiversity metrics (i.e., Species abundance per plot per year; Species presence/absence per plot per year) (See 12C).

7) Spatial aggregation and harmonisation - this includes methods and protocols and the observation design

Analysis was performed at two spatial scales (i.e., site level and habitat level). In order to identify changes in vegetation communities at the habitat level, the available classification of plots in terms of Land use/Land cover (LU/LC) type was used (See 12C and D).

8) Temporal aggregation and harmonisation

Since vegetation data correspond to annual measurements, abiotic variables (measured at finer temporal scales) were aggregated as annual values. The annual average of abiotic variables was calculated based on the average of their trimestral values. This procedure has included the verification

of data quality in terms of intra-annual availability of abiotic in-situ measurements (i.e., trimester per year) (See 12C and D).

9) Gap filling

Not applicable

10) Data documentation including provenance

Folder – ‘DataProducts’ (See 12 A, B, C, D for accompanying descriptive information).

BIODIVERSITY:

A. Data retrieval

v02_spABR.csv

B. Data quality and variables harmonisation

v02_spABR_F.xlsx

v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG.xlsx

C. Data transformation (spatial-temporal aggregation)

v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_sp_abund_pres_abs.xlsx

v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_PLOTS.xlsx

D. Data Analysis (Statistical procedure and data visualisation)

v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_PLOTS.xlsx

LU_LC_plots_character.xlsx

biod_sprich_SITE_HABITAY_LEVEL.xlsx

biod_sprich_Site_habitat_Plots_yearlyPoints.xlsx

sp_rich_time_LU.csv

v02_yearlyPoints.csv

tri_annualPoints_totalrich_2.csv

tri_annualPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv

v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_2.csv

v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv

ABIOTIC:

A. Data retrieval

soil.csv

‘ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015].csv’ in Folder ‘weather’

B. Data cleaning and variables harmonisation /

C. Data transformation (spatial-temporal aggregation)

Soil.xlsx

Weather.xlsx

‘ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015]_T04.csv’ in Folder ‘weather_T04’

D. Data Analysis (Statistical procedure and data visualisation)

abiotic_avrQrtYear_F.csv
 abiotic_avrQrtYear_F_CORREL.csv
 abiotic_graphs 2.xlsx

1) Data ingestion, data storage and persistent identification

Not applicable

2) Workflow documentation and persistent identification

Figure 17. Workflow of data analysis for the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK' (eLTER Plus task 8.1). For more details see the report 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK'.

A. Data retrieval

- Biodiversity Raw database: plant species list and relative abundance, obtained from Pilloto et al. – Database provided by Peter Haase in June 2022 (dataset 'v02_spABR.csv')
- Abiotic Raw datasets: In-situ abiotic measurements of soil chemistry and meteorological data obtained from ECN (downloaded from http://data.ecn.ac.uk/request_form.asp in June 2022) (dataset 'soil.csv' and 'ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015].csv' in folder weather)

B. Data cleaning and variables harmonisation

a. BIODIVERSITY

- Cleaning of original plant species names ('v02_spABR.csv'): DESC_LATIN -> DESC_LATIN_F (Manual removal of text associated to species names, such as growth forms (e.g., Acer campestre {e}, Acer campestre {g}, Acer campestre {s}) and species names in forms other than genus + specific epithet, i.e., of sub-species, hybrids, varieties, vegetation cover, grid reference, etc..).
- Abbreviation of plant species names ('v02_spABR_F.xlsx'): DESC_LATIN_F -> abrev_F (Via R code: criteria of 5 letters (genus) + 5 letters (specific epithet))

R code

```

library('fuzzySim')
library('terra')
library("xlsx")

Dataset_veg <- read.table("v02_spABR.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(Dataset_veg)

Dataset_veg$abbrev_F <- spCodes( Dataset_veg$DESC_LATIN_F, nchar.gen = 5, nchar.sp = 5, nchar.ssp = 3,
sep.species = " ", sep.spcode = " ", verbosity = 2)

write.csv(Dataset_veg, "v02_spABR_F.csv")

```

Note: The automatic abbreviation of species names via R code was followed by a manual abbreviation of species names in the form of sub-species, hybrids and varieties (Table 5). Classifications in the form of vegetation cover, grid reference, etc. were removed from the database (Table 5). In addition, specific abbreviations were assumed to different species which, due to similarity in Latin names, cannot be distinguished according to the criteria of 5 letters (genus) + 5 letters (specific epithet), e.g., *Carex panicea* vs *Carex paniculata* (assumed as *Carex panicea* vs *Carex panicul*) (Table 5).

- Site selection and quality control ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG.xlsx'): Selection of the eLTER site of Moor House (SITE_CODE_NERC = T04) and removal of samples in which the quality of the data has been affected during sampling (i.e., FIELDNAME = Q1, Q2 and Q3).

b. ABIOTIC

- Soil - Site selection and quality control ('soil.xlsx'):
 - Sheet 'Soil_data' – original soil dataset
 - Sheet 'soil_data_T04' - Selection of the eLTER site of Moor House (SITECODE= T04 in Sheet 'Soil_data')
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC' - Removal of samples in which the quality of the data has been affected during sampling (i.e., FIELDNAME = Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5 in Sheet 'soil_data_T04').
- Weather - Site selection and data merging:
 - Selection of the eLTER site of Moor House (SITECODE= T04 via R code) ('ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015]_T04.csv' in Folder 'weather_T04')

```

library('fuzzySim')
library('terra')
library("xlsx")

Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1996.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1997.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1998.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1999.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2000.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2001.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2002.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2003.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2004.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2005.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2006.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2007.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2008.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2009.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2010.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2011.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2012.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2013.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2014.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2015.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")

```

```
Dataset_T04 <- subset (Dataset, Dataset$SITECODE == 'T04')
write.csv(Dataset_T04,"ecn_ma_xxxx_T04.csv")
```

- Merging of T04 weather datasets ('weather.xlsx'): years 1996-2005 in Sheet 'weather96_05' and years 2006-2015 in Sheet 'weather06_15'

C. Data transformation (spatial-temporal aggregation)

a. BIODIVERSITY ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_sp_abund_pres_abs.xlsx'):

- Sheet 'Sp abundance' – Manual calculation of species abundance per plot per year (via sheet 'abund_calc'): this metric is an estimate of species frequency per plot per year: i.e., number of cells in a given plot where the species is present. Note: 10 cells were surveyed in each plot therefore response values range between 0 when the species is absent and 10 when the species is present in all cells of the plot.
- Sheet 'Sp pres abs' – Manual calculation of species presence/absence per plot per year (via Sheet 'Sp abundance' in which cells>0 = 1): in this metric a value of 1 is considered when the species is sampled in at least one cell of a given plot, and absence is considered when the species is not occurring in any cell of the plot.

b. ABIOTIC

- Soil variables ('soil.xlsx')
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC_avr_qtr_YEAR' – Manual calculation of soil chemistry variables; i.e., mean annual values based on the average of trimestral values (via Sheet 'sT04_QC_qtr').
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC_samples_qtr' – Inspection of measurements per trimester per sampling year.
- Weather-related variables (weather.xlsx)
 - Sheet 'w96_05_avr_qtr_YEAR' and 'w06_15_avr_qtr_YEAR' - Manual calculation of weather-related variables; i.e., mean annual values based on the average of trimestral values (via Sheets 'weather96_05' and 'weather06_15').
 - Sheet 'w96_05_samples' – Inspection of measurements per trimester per sampling year (via sheet 'w96_05_samples_qtr').

D. Data Analysis (Statistical procedure and data visualisation)

a. BIODIVERSITY:

- Identification of plots sampled at three-years interval and plots sampled annually ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_PLOTS.xlsx'): Manual identification of plots in which plant sampling was performed in 3-years interval or annually (Sheet 'PLOTS_sampling' via v02_spABR')
- Land Use characterization of sampling plots, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval and 8 plots sampled annually ('LU_LC_plots_charact.xlsx')
- Calculation of temporal trends in total species richness at the site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval and 8 plots sampled annually ('biod_sprich_SITE_HABITAY_LEVEL.xlsx').
- Calculation of temporal trends in species richness at the plot level for 8 plots sampled annually ('biod_sprich_Site_habitat_Plots_yearlyPoints.xlsx').

- Implementation of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, including all pairwise *post-hoc* multiple comparisons at site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval ('sp_rich_time_LU.csv') and 8 plots sampled annually ('v02_yearlyPoints.csv') (via R code):

```

library('lme4')
library('ggResidpanel')
library('sjPlot')
library(DescTools)
library('stats')

##### 45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL

par(mfrow=c(1,2))

##### Site level

Dataset <- read.table("sp_rich_time_LU.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"\"", dec = ".")

###Descriptive analysis

hist(Dataset$sp_rich)

qqnorm(Dataset$sp_rich)
qqline(Dataset$sp_rich)

shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)
ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### p > 0.05 data is normally distributed

### multiple comparisons

teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
teste

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset, main = 'total species richness')

DunnTest(x = Dataset$sp_rich,
          g = Dataset$year)

##### Habitat-level

#Semi-natural grassland

semi_grass <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'Semi-natural grassland')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(semi_grass$sp_rich)
qqnorm(semi_grass $sp_rich)
qqline(semi_grass $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons

teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
teste_grass

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass, main = 'species richness: Semi-natural grassland')

#fen, moor or bog

fen <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'fen, moor or bog')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(fen $sp_rich)
qqnorm(fen $sp_rich)
qqline(fen $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(fen $sp_rich)
ks.test(fen $sp_rich, 'pnorm')

```

```

### multicomparisons
teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
teste_fen
par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen, main = 'species richness: fen, moor or bog')
DunnTest(x = fen$sp_rich, g = fen$year)
#permanent or long-term grassland
perm <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'permanent or long-term grassland')
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(perm $sp_rich)
qqnorm(perm $sp_rich)
qqline(perm $sp_rich)
shapiro.test(perm$sp_rich)
ks.test(perm$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons
teste_perm <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm)
teste_perm
par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm, main = 'permanent or long-term grassland')
#### 8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALLY
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
##### Site level
Dataset <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(Dataset)
###Descriptive analysis
hist(Dataset$sp_rich)
qqnorm(Dataset$sp_rich)
qqline(Dataset$sp_rich)
shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)
ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
### p > 0.05 data is normally distributed
### multiple comparisons
teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
teste
par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset, main = 'total species richness')
DunnTest(x = Dataset$sp_rich,
          g = Dataset$year)
##### habitat level
#Semi-natural grassland
semi_grass <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU == 'Semi-natural grassland')
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(semi_grass$sp_rich)
qqnorm(semi_grass $sp_rich)
qqline(semi_grass $sp_rich)
shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
### multiple comparisons

```

```

teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
teste_grass

par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass, main = 'species richness: Semi-natural grassland')
#fen, moor or bog
fen <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU == 'fen, moor or bog')
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(fen $sp_rich)
qqnorm(fen $sp_rich)
qqline(fen $sp_rich)
shapiro.test(fen $sp_rich)
ks.test(fen $sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons
teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
teste_fen

par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen, main = 'species richness: fen, moor or bog')
DunnTest(x = fen$sp_rich, g = fen$year)
#permanent or long-term grassland
perm <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'permanent or long-term grassland')
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(perm $sp_rich)
qqnorm(perm $sp_rich)
qqline(perm $sp_rich)
shapiro.test(perm$sp_rich)
ks.test(perm$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multicomparisons
teste_perm <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm)
teste_perm

par(mfrow=c(1,1))
boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm, main = 'permanent or long-term grassland')

```

- Implementation of STL decomposition at site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval ('tri_annualPoints_totalrich_2.csv'; 'tri_annualPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv') and 8 plots sampled annually ('v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_2.csv'; 'v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv') (via R code):

```

#ANOMALY DETECTION - OUTLIERS IN TIME SERIES/TEMPORAL TREND#
library(anomalize) #tidy anomaly detection
library(tidyverse) #tidyverse packages like dplyr, ggplot, tidyr
library(tibbletime)
library(tidyquant)

## 45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL
##Site level
data <- read.table("tri_annualPoints_totalrich_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(date = as.POSIXct(strptime(year,"%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

```

```

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = date)
  names(tbl_t)
  class(tbl_t)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich) %>%
  anomalize(remainder) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  filter(anomaly == 'Yes')

####Habitat level

data <- read.table("tri_annualPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(data)

##### fen, moor or bog / mixed / Montane vegetation / permanent or long-term grassland / Semi-natural
grassland

data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'Montane vegetation')

tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(date = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = date)
  names(tbl_t)
  class(tbl_t)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich) %>%
  anomalize(remainder) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  filter(anomaly == 'Yes')

#### 8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALLY

##Site level

data <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(data)

tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)

```

```

names(tbl_t)
class(tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
time_recompose() %>%
plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

#### Habitat level

data <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(data)

##### fen, moor or bog

data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'fen, moor or bog')

tbl <- data %>%
transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)
names(tbl_t)
class(tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
time_recompose() %>%
plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

####Semi-natural grasslands

data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'Semi-natural grassland')

tbl <- data %>%
transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)
names(tbl_t)
class(tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
time_recompose() %>%
plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

```

b. ABIOTIC:

- Implementation of pair-wise correlation using Spearman's rho correlation coefficient ('abiotic_avrQrtYear_F.csv'; 'abiotic_avrQrtYear_F_CORREL') (via R code):

```
vars<-read.table("abiotic_avrQrtYear_F.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
library(Hmisc)
corstarsl <- function(x){
  require(Hmisc)
  x <- as.matrix(x)
  R <- rcorr(x, type="spearman")$r
  p <- rcorr(x, type="spearman")$P

  ## define notions for significance levels; spacing is important.
  mystars <- ifelse(p < .001, "***", ifelse(p < .01, "** ", ifelse(p < .05, "* ", " ")))

  ## truncate the matrix that holds the correlations to two decimal
  R <- format(round(cbind(rep(-1.11, ncol(x)), R), 2))[-1]

  ## build a new matrix that includes the correlations with their appropriate significance values (as stars)
  Rnew <- matrix(paste(R, mystars, sep=""), ncol=ncol(x))
  diag(Rnew) <- paste(diag(R), " ", sep="")
  rownames(Rnew) <- colnames(x)
  colnames(Rnew) <- paste(colnames(x), "", sep="")

  ## remove upper triangle
  Rnew <- as.matrix(Rnew)
  Rnew[upper.tri(Rnew, diag = TRUE)] <- ""
  Rnew <- as.data.frame(Rnew)

  ## remove last column and return the matrix (which is now a data frame)
  Rnew <- cbind(Rnew[1:length(Rnew)-1])
  return(Rnew)
}

corrfinal<- corstarsl(vars)
write.table(corrfinal, "abiotic_avrQrtYear_F_CORREL2.csv", sep = ",")
```

- Graphs of the variation in soil chemistry and weather-related variables across years ('abiotic_graphs 2.xlsx').

c. BIODIVERSITY VS ABIOTIC:

Multivariate Analysis used to (i) disclose gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition; (ii) understand patterns of structure and composition across vegetation types through years; and, (iii) to assess the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities were performed using the default setting of CANOCO Software (version 4.5).

Table 5 - Manual abbreviation (DESC_LATIN_F) of species names in the form of sub-species, hybrids and varieties (DESC_LATIN). Classifications in the form of vegetation cover, grid reference, etc.. were removed from the database (DESC_LATIN_F = Removed).

DESC_LATIN	DESC_LATIN_F
Acer seedling/sp	acer sp
Algal mat	Removed
Alisma plantago-aquatica	alism pla_aqu
Arctium minus ssp pubens	arcti minus pub
Arctostaphylos uva-ursi	arcto uva_ursi
Asplenium ruta-muraria	asple ruta_mur
Athyrium filix-femina	athyr filix_fem
Bare rock (talus)	Removed
Bare soil (including sand)	Removed
Betula seedling/sp	betul sp
Callitriche seedling/sp	calli sp
Calypogeia cf. muelleriana	calyp cf muell
Campylopus atrovirens ssp.sulcatus	campy atrov sul
Capsella bursa-pastoris	capse bursa_pas
Carex panicea	carex panicea
Carex paniculata	carex panicul
Carex seedling/sp	carex sp
Carex viridula ssp scottica	carex virid sco
Cephalozia bicuspidata	cepha bicus
Cephalozia bicuspidata var. lammersiana	cepha bicus lam
Cephalozia connivens	cepha conni
Cephalozia sp	cephalozia sp
Cephaloziella sp	cephaloziella sp
Cladonia cervicornis var verticillata	clado cervi ver
Cladonia ciliata var tenuis	clado cilia ten
Cladonia crispata var cetrariaeformis	clado crisp cet
Cladonia rangiferina	clado rangife
Cladonia rangiformis	clado rangifo
Cochlearia seedling/sp	cochl sp
Dryopteris filix-mas	dryop filix_mas
Equisetum arvense x palustre	equis arv_pal
Euphrasia officinalis agg	euphr offic agg
Eurhynchium praelongum var. stokesii	eurhy prael sto
Festuca ovina/rubra (vegetative)	festuc ovi_rub
Grid reference 100km square	Removed
Grid reference easting	Removed
Hieracium peleteranum (pil)	hiera pelet
Hieracium pilosella ss	hiera pilos

Hypnum cupressiforme ssp resupinatum	hypnu cupre res
Hypnum cupressiforme var cupressiforme	hypnu cupre cup
Hypnum cupressiforme var lacunosum	hypnu cupre lac
Jungermannia exertifolia var cordifolia	junge exert cor
Larix sp.(g)	larix sp
Lathyrus seedling/sp	lathy sp
Limonium binervosum ss	limon biner
Lophocolea sp	lophoc sp
Lophozia cf. ventricosa	lophoz ventri
Lophozia sp	lophoz sp
Luzula campestris/multiflora	luzul cam_mul
Lychnis flos-cuculi	lychn flos_cuc
Moss cover (%)	Removed
Moss height	Removed
Myosotis seedling/sp	myoso sp
Open water (%)	Removed
Peltigera cf. rufescens	pelti cf rufes
Pilosella officinarum agg	pilos offic agg
Pinus seedling/sp	pinus sp
Plagiomnium sp	plagiom sp
Plagiomnium undulatum	plagiom undul
Plagiothecium sp	plagioth sp
Plagiothecium undulatum	plagioth undul
Poa trivialis/nemoralis	poa tri_nem
Polygala sp	polyga sp
Polygonum sp	polygo sp
Ptilium crista-castrensis	ptili cista_cas
Quercus seedling/sp	querc sp
Ranunculus seedling/sp	ranun sp
Ribes uva-crispa	ribes uva_cris
Riccardia/Aneura sp	ric_ane sp
Rosa canina agg.	rosa canin agg
Rosa seedling/sp	rosa sp
Rubus fruticosus agg (g)	rubus fruti agg
Rubus fruticosus agg.	rubus fruti agg
Rubus fruticosus sect. triviales	robust fruti tri
Rumex acetosa	rumex acetosa
Rumex acetosella	rumex acetose
Rumex conglomeratus/sanguineus	rumex com_san
Rumex seedling/sp	rumex sp
Salix atrocinerea x aurita (s)	salix atr_aur
Salix cinerea ssp oleifolia(c)	salix ciner ole

Salix lapponum x atrocinerea (s)	salix lap_atr
Salix repens agg.	salix repen agg
Salix seedling/sp	salix sp
Sample no (thousands)	Removed
Scandix pecten-veneris	scand pecte_ven
Silene alba x dioica	silen alb_dio
Sphagnum auriculatum var auriculatum	sphag auric aur
Sphagnum auriculatum var inundatum	sphag auric inu
Stellaria seedling/sp	stell sp
Taraxacum anglicum (pal)	tarax angli
Taraxacum euryphyllum (spe)	tarax euryp
Taraxacum fulvum (ery)	tarax fulvu
Taraxacum officinale agg.	tarax offic agg
Taraxacum sect. erythrosperma	tarax eryth
Taraxacum simile (ery)	tarax simil
Thuidium abietinum ssp hystricosum	thuid abiet hys
Unidentified broadleaf seedling	Removed
Unidentified conifer seedling	Removed
Unidentified dicot seedling	Removed
Unidentified fern gametophyte	Removed
Unidentified grass seedling	Removed
Unidentified seedling	Removed
Vaccinium vitis-idaea	vacci vitis_ida
Veronica seedling/sp	veron sp
Vicia seedling/sp	vicia sp
Viola riviniana x rupestris	viola riv_rup
Viola riviniana/reichenbachiana	viola riv_rei
Viola seedling/sp	viola sp

8.4 Biogeochemical processes (BGC)

Lauren Gillespie, Eugenio Diaz-Pines & Thomas Dirnböck

8.4.1 Scope

The eLTER PLUS Task 8.2 aims to increase process understanding of the impact of climate change and extreme weather events on carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling and feedbacks in a broad range of ecosystems. To this purpose, data on C and N fluxes were analysed. Further, extreme weather events (i.e., drought) were characterised. It was the goal of the task to facilitate a) identification of critical environmental thresholds and tipping points in C and N turnover and fluxes across the eLTER spectrum of ecosystems, climate zones and socio-ecological contexts and b) improvement of our understanding of the impact of extreme weather events and climate change on ecosystem processes.

8.4.2 Workflow

The aim was to retrieve legacy data from eLTER sites, the workflow included the following steps:

- **data identification:** In order to explore the effects of drought on BGC processes, the data needs for Task 8.2. included time-series data for BGC variables that captured multiple drought events and was long enough to show potential changes in BGC processes (ideally >10 years). Soil moisture and soil temperature data that overlapped temporally the aforementioned variable were also required to be used to identify drought events. Then important auxiliary data (climate, vegetation, plot and soil characterization, etc.) was needed to potentially help explain findings and/or differences between sites. It was also desired to have a homogenous distribution of sites to cover the maximum of habitat types and climatic, pedological, environmental, and social conditions across the European continent.
- **Data retrieval and selection of sites:** The R function '*Function to download B2Drop files directly into R*' was used to import the data directly from B2Drop into R. All data was from individual data files not associated with larger networks (e.g., FLUXNET, ICOS). There were four sites that delivered soil flux data (Hyytiälä SMEAR II, Rosalia Lehrforst, Svartberget, and Zöbelboden), but only two that had >2 years of measurements. These two forest sites, Hyytiälä SMEAR II and Rosalia Lehrforst, provided data for soil CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes as well as soil moisture and soil temperature data that was measured within the vicinity of the GHG flux measurements. Some missing variables were collected via RA activities (e.g., soil hydraulic properties, bulk density)
- **Data trimming:** Since soil moisture and soil temperature data that temporally overlapped the gas flux data was required to identify drought events, soil GHG flux measurement periods without this additional data were not used. Additionally, the models used for data analysis (generalised additive models) required a minimum number of observations per month and no missing years.
- **Data harmonisation:** Dataset structure was harmonised to a long-format and all data was averaged by day to resolve different measurement frequencies
- **Gap filling:** Some *in-situ* soil moisture data had problematic data gaps, and we explored different options to fill them.
- **Quality control and outlier detection:** Although the data had already gone through data quality filters before being delivered, there were still values that appeared odd (impossible values, appeared to be caused by machine malfunction, etc.). Site managers were contacted to verify that these values were indeed incorrect and give the green light to remove them.
- **Dataset publication:** The dataset, including the soil GHG fluxes, soil moisture, soil temperature, precipitation, air temperature, soil characteristic (soil texture, soil type, etc.), site information, and additional metadata for the two sites analysed, will be made publicly available online (B2Drop or B2Share) with documentation including data sources, column descriptions, how data was transformed from original data delivered, etc.

Figure 18. Prototype workflow for the BGC Science Case integrating soil water, soil temperature and soil respiration data as input for data analysis

8.5 ForestSinkCalculator

Johannes Kobler & Ivo Offenthaler

8.5.1 Scope

The Allosaur – an online tool for calculating tree biomass with allometric functions

As trees convert atmospheric CO₂ to organic carbon (C) and partly sequester it in long-term pools such as stems, branches and coarse roots, living trees act as C sinks during their lifespan (Luyssaert et al. 2007; Anderson-Teixeira et al. 2021). Additionally, undisturbed forests have been found to sequester more C during their long lifetime than losing C via heterotrophic respiration (Luyssaert et al. 2008; Pregitzer und Euskirchen 2004). Thus, forests have been defined as C sinks and may be considered in obligatory national greenhouse gas budgets (Janssens et al. 2003; Schlamadinger et al. 2007).

A crucial part of forest C balancing is the quantification of biomass/C stored in the tree compartments such as stem, branch, coarse roots, foliage and fine root (Ohtsuka et al. 2007). Generally, these numbers are estimated with species- and compartment-specific allometric functions of forest inventory parameters such as diameter at breast height (DBH) and tree height (Neumann et al. 2016; Zianis et al. 2005). Unlike the measurement of the input parameters in the field, the selection and application of these allometric functions require higher professional expertise and data-management skills (Neumann et al. 2016).

The Allosaur is a user-friendly online tool to estimate tree biomass. Estimates are given at stand level for total biomass, above- and belowground fractions, and compartments such as stem, branches, coarse roots, foliage and fine roots. The calculation is based on forest inventory data (tree species, diameter at breast height, tree height) and is available for ten common European forestry species²⁵ (spruce, beech, fir, ash, ..). Beyond these estimates, the tool offers a rich interface for the visual exploration of single tree data which offers users an instant plausibility check.

8.5.2 Workflow

Data acquisition and preparation

Prior to the forest survey, at least one representative plot of the studied forest ecosystem has to be selected and marked. On this plot, tree species, DBH (mm), height (m), and vitality (living, dying, dead) are inventoried. For longitudinal surveys it is advantageous to geolocate the trees and tag them with numbered metal plates.

Subsequently, data have to be structured and formatted to conform with the eLTER data format which favours long over wide data²⁶ (Peterseil, J., Geiger, S. 2020). In short, the surveyed parameters of each tree are listed row-wise, whereas each surveyed value (column VALUE) is linked to the parameter by specifying the name of the parameter in the column PARAMETER. The other columns of the file STATION_CODE, OBJECT_ID, TAXA, TIME, PLOTSIZE and UNIT specifies the ID of the study plot, the ID of the surveyed tree, the species of the respective tree, the timestamp of the forest inventory, the size of the study plot and the unit of the value.

²⁵ P. abies, A. alba, P. sylvestris, L. decidua, F. sylvatica, A. pseudoplatanus, F. excelsior, U. glabra, S. aria, B. pendula

²⁶ see <https://www.statology.org/long-vs-wide-data/>

Data upload and import

Data can be provided via file upload or direct pasting from the clipboard. A number of common data file formats (delimited text, MS Excel, SPSS, RDS) are accepted for upload. Uploaded/pasted data can be previewed live and preprocessed (change of data type, variable selection and renaming) in the upload dialogue. Users can select an example dataset to instantly access the remaining features.

Figure 19. Import and update features

Calculation

After confirmation of the upload, data explorer and biomass table view are enabled, while species- and compartment-specific allometric functions are evaluated with the uploaded data (Kobler et al. 2015; Kobler et al. 2019). Where required, oven dry volume is derived from volume by applying species-specific shrinking factors (ÖNORM EN 13556). Similarly, dry volume is converted to dry mass with tree species-specific wood densities (ÖNORM EN 13556). Individual tree biomasses are then upscaled to area (kg ha^{-1}) from the area of the inventoried plot (column: PLOTSIZE) and labelled with the suffix “_specific”. Calculated values are merged with the uploaded data, which can be downloaded after calculation as a zipped csv-file.

The tabulated summary can be viewed or copied for direct inclusion in office software in the summary tab.

Exploration

The exploration tab offers a fully featured visual data explorer (Figure 20). Users can select from a variety of plots to inspect distribution and association of variables (with the option to customise the chart for download as an image file, or copy the code to reproduce the graph in R²⁷) (Meyer, F., Perrier, V. 2022).

²⁷ R language for statistical computing: <https://www.r-project.org/>

Figure 20. Data can be explored with a variety of plots in the “explore” tab.

Export

Results can be downloaded, and a formatted summary table can readily be transferred to office software via the clipboard (Figure 21).

Tree biomass											
	300			700			2900				
	2003	2007	2012	2014	2003	2007	2014	2019	2012	2014	2019
aboveground											
foliage	20.91	18.19	17.65	17.12	20.41	19.15	19.43	19.79	29.24	29.79	29.98
branches	45.60	40.12	41.40	40.35	72.97	69.68	74.33	77.39	51.47	52.60	54.13
stem	269.6	255.0	247.9	233.1	253.8	232.1	241.6	247.8	306.7	327.5	335.8
total	336.10	313.33	306.95	290.61	347.20	320.94	335.32	344.98	387.46	409.88	419.90
belowground											
coarse roots	92.56	85.03	84.44	84.55	63.43	59.99	60.07	62.18	113.9	121.4	126.5
fine roots	94.26	84.13	81.36	77.66	102.7	93.23	89.82	90.86	95.24	98.09	99.37
total	186.82	169.16	165.79	162.21	166.13	153.21	149.89	153.04	209.10	219.45	225.90
grand total	522.92	482.49	472.74	452.82	513.33	474.15	485.21	498.02	596.56	629.33	645.80

unit: tons per hectare (100 g / m²)

copy table

Figure 21. A formatted summary on plot level can be transferred to office software via the clipboard.

8.5.3 Forest inventory data of the eLTER site Zöbelboden - test case

Study area

The 90-ha studied catchment is known as Austrian LTER site “Zöbelboden” located within the “National Park Kalkalpen” (<https://deims.org/8eda49e9-1f4e-4f3e-b58e-e0bb25dc32a6>). Mean annual air temperature is 8.2°C. Annual precipitation ranges from 980 to 2200 mm. Snowfall occurs between October and May. Topographically, the site (90 ha) is comprised by a plateau (850–956 m a.s.l.) and a steep north to north-west facing slope (30–70°) extending from 850 m down to 550 m a.s.l. The potential natural vegetation of the plateau, beech-fir mixed forest, has largely been replaced by planted a Norway spruce, *Picea abies* (L.) Karst., after the mixed forest was clear-cut in 1910. The forest stand is intermingled with European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) trees. The forest on the slope is a near-

natural mixed beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) forest with ash (*Fraxinus excelsior* L.), maple (*Acer pseudoplatanus* L.) and spruce [*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.] as the most frequent additional tree species. At the plateau, soils are mainly chromic cambisols and hydromorphic stagnosols (pseudogley). At the slopes, lithic or rendzic leptosols (rendsina) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2006). Triassic dolomite is the predominant bedrock material, partly interspersed with limestone plate layers. Since the establishment of the monitoring site at Zöbelboden in 1992, management has been restricted to the removal of bark beetle infested trees at the plateau.

Plot design of the LTER site Zöbelboden

The forest ecosystems within the study site were monitored by two climate stations at a clearing area, a measurement tower (ca. 42 m) and three Intensive monitoring plots (IP) within the mentioned two representative forest ecosystems. The Intensive monitoring plots 1 (IP1) and 3 (IP3) were installed in 1993 and 2008 in close vicinity on the almost flat plateau at about 950 m a.s.l. to monitor the even-aged Norway spruce stand. In 2008 IP1 had to be replaced by IP3 due to severe wind- and bark beetle damage at the IP1. Within both plots, soil types vary on a small scale between Lithic to Rendzic Leptosols and Chromic Cambisols, with partly stagnic properties (WRB 2006). Mull and moder humus forms predominate. The Intensive plot 2 (IP2) was installed at the north-exposed upper part of the slopes of the Zöbelgraben catchment to monitor the mentioned near-natural temperate deciduous forest of the catchment. Due to the steepness (~36°) of the slopes, the soils consist of shallow Lithic and Rendzic Leptosols (mean soil depth: ~0.12 m). Mull and moder humus predominate at the site, indicating relatively fast litter turnover (Jost et al., 2011). The number of trees partly decreased during the last 30 years due to forest disturbance events such as wind throw, bark beetle and drought.

Within the IPs, the trees were geolocated and tagged with numbered metal plates. Several forest inventories were conducted in 1993, 2005, 2014 and 2019 at the IPs. The survey comprised the forest inventory parameters tree species, diameter at breast height (DBH in mm), tree height (m), and vitality (living, dying, dead).

8.5.4 References

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8.6 Climate-Water-Food Nexus (CWF) - Task 8.3

Nikos Nikolaidis

8.6.1 Scope

WP8 aims at examining the impacts of “extreme events” at two scales: the field and catchment scales. Task 8.3 aims to improve the knowledge of the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and to understand relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. Data from 10 well-instrumented sites that cross climatic, geological, and socio-ecological regions were used to test resilience indicators, such as WUE, nutrient use efficiency, soil structure and function. This analysis was conducted on three levels:

1. Time series analysis of flux tower data
2. Modelling with 1D models (1D-ICZ, CLM5.0)
3. Modelling with watershed scale models (SWAT, CLM, INCA)

Integrated models are used to calculate the ecosystem WUE and simulate sites to:

- Assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems;
- Analyse the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover single and multiple droughts;
- Assess the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience, and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts;
- Assess the strengths and weaknesses of the RI design to derive resilience indicators.

8.6.2 Workflow

The following steps compose the workflow to retrieve legacy data from eLTER sites to be used in the models (here for the 1D-ICZ model as an example, see below for a more detailed description) (see also Figure 22):

- **Data identification:** Making a list of the input parameters, their time series and units that are needed for the 1D-ICZ model (Table 6)
- **Data retrieval:** Retrieving the parameters (meteorology, soil parameters, nutrient fluxes etc.) from the available datasets (eLTER Repository/B2Drop, FLUXNET/ICOS) and scientific papers.

- **Temporal aggregation and unit transformation:** Transforming the original parameters time series and units to fit the model requirements (i.e., usually monthly time series are needed). For example, transformation of the daily temperature (°C) to monthly temperature by taking the average of daily data, or converting the nutrient fluxes from mg L⁻¹ to mol L⁻¹ by using the molecular mass of the nutrient.
- **Gap filling:** Filling of the missing data by taking average values between days or months if possible or even transferring data back, forth, back to back to complete the time series.
- **Data fusion / spatial aggregation:** In case of unavailability of multiple essential parameters for a specific eLTER site, and if possible, filling the missing parameters with measured data from another eLTER site (data fusion). To do so, soil properties, meteorology etc. are compared between the sites to find similarities and differences. The differences are then accounted for in the analysis and interpretation of the results.
- **Quality control (1) via temporal aggregation:** Further check of the data by converting monthly time series to yearly time series, finding average values for each year and making diagrams to visualise the data time series.
- **Quality control (2) based on literature review and (3) with other sites:** Comparison of data estimates for each parameter with data from scientific papers or/and data comparison between the eLTER sites.
- **Data storage** and preparation of the input files needed for the 1D-ICZ model.

Figure 22. Task 8.3 data workflow processing steps for the 1D-ICZ model.

Table 6. Input parameters for 1D-ICZ sub-models

Parameter name	Timestep	Units	Model
Precipitation	Monthly time series	m	HYDRUS-1D
Evapotranspiration	Monthly time series	m	HYDRUS-1D
Air temperature	Monthly time series	°C	HYDRUS-1D PROSUM
Bulk density	-	g m ⁻³	HYDRUS-1D
	-	kg m ⁻³	CAST
Soil chemistry: Ca, Mg, Na, K, H ⁺ , F, NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Initial (for the first simulation month)	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Precipitation chemistry: Ca, Mg, Na, K, H ⁺ , Al, SO ₄ ²⁻ , F, NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Monthly time series	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
Silt-clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
PAR (photosynthetic active radiation)	Monthly time series	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PROSUM

For the three selected sites of Zöbelboden, Hyytiala, and Svartberget, the data retrieval and transformation were performed as follows:

Zöbelboden: All the necessary data for the simulation were retrieved from the eLTER Depository (B2Drop). The input time series of precipitation were calculated by summing up daily values to monthly values and converting them from mm to m. The input time series of temperature were estimated by taking the monthly average from daily data. The input time series of PAR were calculated by eliminating all zeros, by taking the average of the remaining half-hourly data and by dividing the values with 0.217 to convert them from W m⁻² to μmol m⁻² s⁻¹.

Hyttiala: All the necessary data for the simulation were retrieved from FLUXNET and the eLTER Depository (B2Drop). The input time series of precipitation was calculated by summing up daily values to monthly values and by converting them from mm to m. The monthly time series of temperature and latent heat (LE) were retrieved intact from FLUXNET. However, the values of LE were converted from W m⁻² to m using the latent heat of vaporization (λ). The input time series of PAR was calculated as the day time average by eliminating all the zeros and by taking the monthly average of the remaining data.

Svartberget: All the necessary data for the simulation were retrieved from FLUXNET and the eLTER Depository (B2Drop). The input time series of precipitation was calculated by summing up daily values to monthly values and converting them from mm to m. The monthly time series of temperature, latent heat (LE) and PAR were retrieved from the FLUXNET database. ET (evapotranspiration) was calculated from flux tower latent heat data using the latent heat of vaporization (λ).

For the majority of the parameters, no gap filling was conducted. However, we used available gap filled data for some of the parameters needed (as inputs or as field data for calibration purposes) such as precipitation, temperature, GPP etc.

The only site for which we needed to perform gap filling was Zöbelboden. The Zöbelboden site had latent heat flux measurements from 2014 to 2020. In order to simulate the site for the 1996-2020 period over which all other data were available, we used the Penman-Monteith equation and compared the ET estimates against the latent heat flux measurements. The parameters of the equation (r_a and r_s) were adjusted to obtain ET estimates as close as possible to the cumulative latent heat flux measurements.

Gap filling

For the majority of parameters, no gap filling was conducted. However, we did use available gap filled data for some of the parameters needed (as inputs or as field data for calibration purposes) such as precipitation, temperature, GPP etc.

The only site we did perform gap filling for was Zöbelboden. The Zöbelboden site had latent heat flux measurements from 2014 to 2020. In order to simulate the site for the 1996-2020 period of available data we used the Penman-Monteith equation and compared the ET estimates against the latent heat flux measurement. The parameters of the equation (r_a and r_s) were adjusted so the ET estimates to be as close to the cumulative latent heat flux measurements as possible.

8.6.3 Evapotranspiration Calculation

Source: Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., Raes, D., & Smith, M. (1998). Crop evapotranspiration - Guidelines for computing crop water requirements. FAO Irrigation and drainage Paper 56. <http://www.fao.org/3/x0490e/x0490e00.htm>

Evapotranspiration (ET) can be calculated from latent heat (LE) by dividing by latent heat of vaporisation (λ)

$$ET = \frac{LE}{\lambda}$$

This assumes density of water equal to 1000 kg m⁻³. Latent heat of vaporisation is the amount of energy needed to change a unit mass of water from liquid to water vapour. With LE and λ in units of MJ m⁻² T⁻¹ and MJ kg⁻¹, respectively, ET is in units of kg m⁻² T⁻¹ which is equal to depth of water in mm T⁻¹. Latent heat of vaporisation varies slightly with temperature, but is often set to 2.45 MJ kg⁻¹ which is the value for an air temperature of 20 °C. Allen et al. (1998) also provides an equation for calculating λ with air temperature variation:

$$\lambda = 2.501 - (2.361 \times 10^{-3}) \times Ta$$

where, Ta is air temperature in °C and λ is in MJ kg⁻¹.

The evapotranspiration rate is converted to mm day⁻¹ from MJ m⁻² day⁻¹ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ET \text{ (Evapotranspiration)} &= \frac{LE \text{ (Latent heat flux)}}{\lambda \text{ (Latent heat of vaporisation)}} = \frac{LE}{\lambda} \left(\frac{\frac{W}{m^2}}{\frac{MJ}{kg}} \right) \\ &= 0.0864 * \frac{LE}{\lambda} \left(\frac{mm}{day} \right) \end{aligned}$$

8.7 Climate-Water-Food-Nexus (CWF) - Task 9.3

Christian Poppe & Alexandre Belleflamme

8.7.1 Scope

Task 9.3 aims to establish a validated pan-European scale terrestrial ecosystem model using eLTER network data, assess the impact of climate extremes on water related ecosystem services, and provide 30 years of reanalysed time series of hydrological fluxes. First, we have set-up the CLM5 land-surface model for the pan-European domain at 3 km resolution and run it for a 24-year simulation. Then, we have validated the model runs against eLTER site's time series (Task 8.3). The climatic forcing data at this resolution were obtained by using a disaggregation scheme from large scale reanalyses. In addition to available time series from the eLTER network, we have used remotely sensed time series in

cooperation with WP4 (e.g., SMOS, SMAP, Copernicus Hub services such as Sentinel data) and global soil moisture products (e.g., ESA CCI). The approach allows us to demonstrate the concept of ecosystem reanalysis for soil moisture time series, and the assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the current eLTER network design regarding the impact of climate extremes on water related ecosystem services.

8.7.2 Workflow

The workflow for retrieving and using legacy data from eLTER, ICOS, and FLUXNET in order to validate remote sensed and simulated data can be summarised in the following main steps (a more detailed description of the workflow is provided below):

- **Data identification:** Identification of stations providing already harmonised and gap-filled legacy data.
- **Data retrieval:** Retrieval of the time series via the B2Share facility.
- **Extraction of quality checked data:** In each time series, selection of measured and high-quality gap-filled data only, on the basis of a quality control flag.
- **Unit transformation:** Conversion of latent heat to evapotranspiration.

The 3km European CLM5-BGC model (from here: CLM5EU3) land-surface characterization was set up using default datasets from remote sensing (Lawrence et al., 2019). Scripts to retrieve and map these datasets to the user-specified resolutions are provided with the CLM5 installation. Importantly, CLM5 estimates initial carbon pool balance by equilibrating carbon uptake and output fluxes over a long period of time (~1500 simulation years). All model runs were conducted on the JURECA HPC facility of the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC). A full documentation of CLM5EU3 install, setup, spin-up and production workflow will be published in DataLabs and/or GitLab with the second scientific publication of this Task (CLM5EU3 model evaluation).

In the meantime, existing spatiotemporal remote sensing and reanalysis data on ecosystem processes were downloaded to JSC (using given APIs where possible and semi-automatic scripts for all others), such as:

1. **GLASS:** gross primary production, evapotranspiration and leaf-area index;
2. **GLEAM:** evapotranspiration, transpiration, surface and root layer soil moisture;
3. **ERA5-Land:** evapotranspiration, transpiration, surface and subsurface soil moisture;
4. **COSMO-REA6:** temperature, humidity, precipitation, radiation, pressure, windspeed.

As these datasets have differing original file formats, dimension order, numeric type, time and space resolution, we determined common dimensions, numeric types and aggregated them to one common dataset by bilinear spatial interpolation and averaging to 8-daily means, to streamline comparisons with the upcoming CLM5EU3 outputs. Where necessary, we converted the original units (e.g., GLASS latent heat in [W/m²] to evapotranspiration in [mm/day]). The resulting netcdf4 dataset has therefore 3km and 8-daily time resolution for all variables listed above over the 1995-2018 period and can possibly be published as scientific dataset. Bash, NCL and Python scripts used to download and process the variables to the common dataset will be published on DataLabs and/or GitLab.

We validated the ecosystems processes (gross primary production, evapotranspiration and transpiration) original data and the processing to the new dataset by comparisons with in-situ eddy covariance measurements. We wrote a script to semi-automatically download aggregated datasets from the eLTER, FLUXNET and ICOS networks, namely:

1. **FLUXNET2015:** gross primary production, latent heat;
2. **ICOS Drought2018:** gross primary production, latent heat.

Those datasets offer already harmonised and gap-filled time series, for 50-60 stations in the European domain. Time series length differs between stations, depending on the setup and calibration of the measurement devices and the time series often include quality control variables. We extracted the corresponding variables for latent heat and gross primary production and masked the time series to keep only measured or high-quality gap-filled values. We again converted latent heat to evapotranspiration [mm/day].

To compare the in-situ measurements with estimations from the spatial dataset, we selected the grid cell which is closest to the measurement station (coordinates are in metadata given by the network) and extract the time series from that grid cell. We calculated statistical assessments, e.g., the coefficient of determination, root mean square error and percent bias between the in-situ and grid cell remote sensing data. If required by, e.g., low correlation or high bias values, the land cover of the grid cell was examined based on MODIS data. If the area of matching land cover with the corresponding eddy covariance footprint land cover in the chosen grid cell was low, we compared surrounding grid cells for the best match (highest coverage of in-situ data correspondent land cover). After that, we proceeded with the analysis pipeline by dividing gross primary production by evapotranspiration, yielding water-use efficiency (WUE) and comparing drought (low soil moisture) WUE and non-drought WUE to determine ecosystem function drought response. In future, we will take a closer look at the representation of this ecosystem function variability in the outputs of the CLM5EU3 and improve it by statistical considerations of model and observation biases into an ecosystem reanalysis.

8.8 Socio-ecological Systems (SES) - Agent based modelling

Veronika Gaube & Bastian Bertsch-Hörmann

8.8.1 Scope

The T8.4 Science Case addresses the analysis of local-to-regional land-use actors and other relevant stakeholders of the local land-use system. Analysis aims at identification of key stakeholder groups and the qualitative description of their positions within the socio-ecological system. Special emphasis is put on their perceptions of and vulnerability to major environmental problems, climate change impacts and risks, as well as the implementation of actual/potential adaptation measures. A second focus is set on the land-use related communication between stakeholder groups, detailing the connections between land users and their communication partners. The analysis contributes to a holistic system-understanding necessary for the implementation of a land-use ABM with a focus on climate change adaptation, land-use decision making and social learning. The research design is based on a mixed-method approach using qualitative semi-structured expert interviews and content analysis, as well as a quantitative online survey and social network analysis.

Agent based modelling (ABM)

The purpose of the ABM SECLAND is the study of systemic feedbacks between external changes in the socio-political, biophysical, and climatic framework conditions and the internal dynamics arising from the decision-making of farm agents and its effects on the land-use dynamics of the study region. The farm agents pursue well-being as the balance between workload and income and as a distinct feature, the model incorporates the 'value system' of a farmer as essential influence on the decision-making process. Diverse farming objectives (e.g., economic success, nature conservation) affect farmer's decision-making and are reflected in the agent-based model as farming styles.

For the setup of the ABM, we rely on the complementary combination of quantitative and qualitative data. The main quantitative source is the InVekos (IACS) data that we use for the initialization of farm

structure. Farm areas are based on spatially explicit land-use information on parcels provided by the InVekos GIS-data. Subsidies, farm and livestock classification, numbers and densities (e.g., livestock units per hectare, lu/ha) are drawn from the aggregated analysis of reported InVekos numbers. We rely on production-region related yield data from the bookkeeping farms (“Buchführungsbetriebe”). For missing values and to compute gross margins, we use price and cost and labour requirement information on state/federal level (BAB, 2021). For other socio-economic inputs (farmers age, off-farm income etc.) we use data from Statistik Austria. We rely on qualitative data to understand farmers’ motivations and relevant management actions, which is a common approach in agent-based modelling.

Inputs for the ABM are (a) quantitative data (land use and owner/actors structure) and (b) qualitative data (identification and characterisation of stakeholders/actors).

8.8.2 Workflow

8.8.2.1 Land-use and owner structure for a specified region

Gap-free land-use dataset with assignment of owner structure as input to the ABM. The resolution of the dataset is a single land unit which is subject to management and decision. This can be a single field, grassland parcel or forest stand. The issue is that not all the information can be obtained from one data source but rather being an integration of existing data sources (e.g., LPIS)

The dataset in principle on a minimum level contains the following information: parcel identifier (e.g., SCHLAG_ID), land-use per parcel (category), actor identifier (anonymised), and actor classification (category)

Normally, no platform specific data are collected covering the whole space of the LTSER region. Therefore, national scale as well as European scale data are used to develop a proxy for the land use and owner structure for the region as input to the agent-based model. This could be considered a ‘scientific data product’ which could be shared using the eLTER RI services.

Data retrieval

Data are retrieved either by direct access of GIS Data (WFS/OGC) or a shape file / geodatabase retrieved as open government data (OGD) and are retrieved from <https://eurodatacube.com/marketplace/data-products/lpis>.

Landuse and landowner data

Data are based on the IACS (Integrated Agriculture Control System) provided by the member states. For Austria the LPIS (Land Parcel Information System, INVEKOS) was used. These include land use categories as well as the basic landowner structure. LPIS is only covering those management parcels (Schläge) which receive funding under the national implementation of CAP (Common Agricultural policy). This includes Land use categories and management structure (based on IACS LPIS) by management unit and Land ownership structure (which area belongs to whom). For forestry, settlement and sealed areas CORINE Land Cover has been taken as proxy, as no easy to access public datasets are available.

Gap filling / compilation

Land use and management structure - As LPIS is only covering land use management parcels for which measures under the different national implementations of the CAP are implemented, not all parcels are covered by the dataset. Missing information is completed by using larger scale land cover datasets

as CORINE landcover of the most appropriate time period. Data for other land use/cover categories are compiled into one dataset (Agriculture, forestry & settlement and built-up areas)

Land ownership structure - If the landowner structure cannot be directly received, this could be collected as basic data from a survey of the region, or allocation by algorithm (number of farms, size distribution, land use distribution).

Harmonisation

Data format harmonisation included the integration of tabular and spatial data in a GIS (geopackage). Every land parcel is assigned a unique identifier, parcels are then linked to farm businesses (businesses represent actors in the ABM, classified according to farm types)

Variable harmonisation is done on the common data model.

Content harmonisation is done by defining the level of detail of the land use categories (e.g., arable land, grassland, fallow land) as well as harmonising land use categories (based on expert-based knowledge using the classification national land use types (SNA, Schlagnutzungsarten) based on IACS/LPIS as well as European Scale classifications, e.g., CORINE, HILUCS (Land Use Categories).

Quality assurance

No quality assurance, as it is mainly based on IACS / Basic data are basically quality assured / Problem of quality assurance because there are no good comparative values (e.g., CORINE Land Cover due to different spatial resolution).

8.8.2.2 Stakeholder and social network analysis

Identification and qualitative description of key land-use stakeholder groups, their perception of land-use change and connected environmental problems, of climate change impacts and risks, as well as actual/potential adaptation measures. These data will be used to select adequate sub-systems/sectors to be modelled, to derive relevant actor groups for the ABM and to generate insights to formalise the land-use decision-making process, the role of framework conditions and the formulation of future scenarios, in particular with regard to extreme weather events and climate change adaptation.

Quantitative description of the land-use social network and related communication between different stakeholder groups serves to define in more detail how land-use decision makers are influenced by their connections within the social network. This allows to formalise in the ABM the role of social learning and the exchange of information between specific stakeholder groups in the context of land-use decision making.

8.8.2.2.1 Expert interviews (qualitative)

Data retrieval / collection

The data collection is done via semi-structured expert interviews to identify relevant land users in a region, their positions, and perceptions. Standardised interviews with local experts are conducted using an interview guideline (comparability across platforms). This process included the creation of the questionnaires, conducting the interviews (online via "Zoom", or in person facilitated by LTSER platform manager), and collection of the interview recordings (sound files).

Transcription and digitization

The transcription of the interview was done automated in the respective national language using the online transcription service "sonix.ai" to transcribe interview recordings. This included the manual

review and quality control of the transcription process as well as the linguistic translation of the interview transcript using an automated AI algorithm. The online translation service “DeepL” was used to translate national language into English, resulting in a written English interview transcript.

Content analysis and classification

The content analysis of interview transcripts done in “Atlas.ti” software which is an open coding tool to identify keywords (codes) and coding of text passages. This included the iterative arrangement of quotes in categories/sub-categories as well as the (a) identification of central themes regarding land-use change and connected environmental problems, climate change impacts, risks and vulnerability, adaptation measures, (b) the definition of relevant stakeholder groups, positions, perceptions, (c) identification of which stakeholders are there in the region, and do they qualify for an active role (actor) or a passive role (part of framework/environment) in the ABM.

This results in the potential data products (a) **identification of relevant stakeholders for a region** and (b) **qualitative description of land-use systems**.

Quality assurance

- Manual control of the results of the different work steps.
- Codebook

Variable (semantic) harmonisation

Variable harmonisation, e.g., of the actors which are currently national and not across the platforms as well as harmonisation of administrative units.

8.8.2.2.2 Social network analysis (quantitative)

Data retrieval / collection

Data collection is done via standardised quantitative online surveys for the target groups of the local land-users and related stakeholders in order to analyse connections and communication between land users and other stakeholder groups. For the questionnaire creation we used the online tool “LimeSurvey”. Difficulties arose to find enough individuals willing to fill out the survey to reach minimum sample size (in this case $N > 50$). The Platform Management Support is needed and contacts are necessary.

Data extraction and manipulation

This included (a) the extraction of survey data, (b) the manipulation to enable import into social network software tool “Gephi” (specific table structure necessary, definition of nodes and edges), and (c) the review and quality control of the manipulation and import process done manually

Network analysis

Visual and statistical analysis of social networks in “Gephi” resulting in a potential data product on the description of social networks using network graphs and network metrics.

Quality assurance

Manual control of the results of the different work steps.

8.9 Socio-ecological Systems (SES) - Land cover

Will Bolton & Jan Dick

8.9.1 Scope

Task 4.5 aims to pilot and evaluate the regular provision of vital data from central RI hubs to individual partner sites/platforms. Six LTSER platforms tested the provision of central services using land cover and population statistics datasets as a proof of concept.

8.9.2 Workflow

The general workflow was:

- identify data
- collect data
- clean data (if applicable)
- filter data to site boundaries of the 6 LTSER platforms
- produce summary statistics and visualisations/plots
- share new data products

The identified data sources for piloting were:

- GHS-POP population (<https://doi.org/10.2905/D6D86A90-4351-4508-99C1-CB074B022C4A>)
- EUROSTAT data (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>)
 - Area under tillage
 - GDP per capita
 - Population density
- Corine Land Cover (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc2018>)

These were retrieved manually and stored in the DataLabs system (see above).

Data cleaning was necessary for the EUROSTAT data as it did not meet some technical requirements for the cookie-cutter system used to process it. Placeholder values were made blank (":" changed to ""), NUTS/LAU region IDs were reformatted for machine reading (e.g., "BE212 - Arr. Mechelen" changed to "BE212") and moved to the first column.

Each dataset was then processed by the cookie-cutter system which split it into 6 datasets, one for each LTSER platform.

For each site, the site-specific datasets were then plotted using GIS software (QGIS or Python's matplotlib package). A summary statistic was also produced using Python's Rasterio package for the land cover datasets as follows:

- For Corine land cover, a text file was produced summarising the total area of each land cover type within the site boundaries
- For GHS-POP, a text file was produced describing the total population within the site boundaries (i.e., the sum of the values of the cropped dataset)

For each site, the full set of datasets, visualisations and summaries was then uploaded to Google Drive to be shared with the relevant stakeholders.

9 Annex B - State of the art - detailed description

9.1 e-infrastructure workflows and services

EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a digital infrastructure that offers a range of services to support research data management and analysis. EOSC provides a variety of tools and services that can help researchers in managing their data workflows, including data storage, sharing, and analysis. The EOSC provides a range of services for the scientific community to address their data management and analysis needs, e.g.

- **Data storage and management:** EOSC provides a variety of data storage and management services that help researchers store and manage their research data. For instance, the EOSC offers the EOSC-Hub, which provides researchers with access to a range of data storage resources, including cloud storage services, data repositories, and data archives. Researchers can use these resources to store and manage their research data, including large datasets.
- **Data sharing:** EOSC provides researchers with tools and platforms that enable them to share their research data with others. The EOSC-Hub, for example, offers the Science Mesh, which is a secure and reliable communication platform that enables researchers to share their data and collaborate with others in real-time. Additionally, the EOSC provides tools and services that help researchers to ensure that their data is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), making it easier for others to discover and reuse their data.
- **Data analysis:** EOSC provides researchers with tools and platforms that enable them to analyse their research data. For instance, the EOSC-Hub offers a range of data analysis tools, including cloud-based platforms, such as Jupyter Notebooks, RStudio, and KNIME, which enable researchers to run complex data analyses in the cloud. Additionally, EOSC provides access to high-performance computing (HPC) resources, which researchers can use to run computationally-intensive analyses.
- **Data visualisation:** EOSC provides researchers with tools and platforms that enable them to visualise their research data. For instance, the EOSC-Hub offers a range of data visualisation tools, including platforms like Plotly, D3.js, and Matplotlib, which enable researchers to create interactive and engaging visualisations of their data.
- **Training and support:** EOSC provides researchers with training and support services to help them use the various tools and services provided by the EOSC. For instance, the EOSC-Hub offers training courses and webinars on topics such as data management, data analysis, and data visualisation. Additionally, the EOSC provides researchers with technical support and assistance in using the various tools and services provided by EOSC.

A first screening of relevant services described in the EOSC marketplace was also carried out. The EOSC marketplace²⁸ is a platform providing information about and access to resources for various research domains along with integrated data analytics tools. Before the screening process, relevant criteria to be evaluated were defined. A total of 79 services are listed under the category “physical & eInfrastructures”, of which 55 belong to the subcategory “Compute” and 20 to “Data Storage”. These 75 services were screened.

²⁸ see <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

The services identified as being most relevant to eLTER were all related to data storage, e.g., EUDAT services (like B2SHARE, D2DROP, B2SAFE or B2FIND) or Zenodo as generic trusted data repository. However, all of these free to use services are already in use by eLTER.

LifeWatch

LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium providing e-Science research facilities to scientists investigating biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services in order to support society in addressing key planetary challenges. The LifeWatch ERIC was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium by the European Commission in 2017.

LifeWatch ERIC is a **distributed research infrastructure and a VRE**. The consortium is composed of eight European Union Member States. LifeWatch ERIC's members operate from national nodes, known as Distributed Centres, while its Common Facilities are located in three Member States: Spain (Statutory Seat & ICT-Core), Italy (Service Centre) and the Netherlands (VLab & Innovations Centre).

Virtual Research Environment (VRE) - The LifeWatch Species Information Backbone (LW-SIBb) facilitates the standardisation of species data and the (virtual) integration of the many distributed biodiversity data repositories and operating facilities. Built on expert validated and literature-based information, the LW-SIBb is structured in different open data systems for taxonomy, biogeography, genetics, and species traits. The LW-SIBb is the driving force behind the species information services of the Belgian LifeWatch.be e-Lab.

Access to data: LifeWatch ERIC website provides access to 1502 datasets from 11 research sites. Data can be accessed and used mainly within the VRE, and downloaded as a registered user. VRE users can publish their derived data products and other resources in the RI with a DOI.

Available **data formats** are Comma-separated values (CSV), Darwin Core Archive, HTML, KML, and PDF. Datasets can be browsed through the metadata catalogue, and data are used with the provided services, but the original data are not always available for download (via the RI, it is mostly available from the original source).

Services

Services are designed to cover the entire process (from selection, to downloading, to viewing and analysis) and required to work with remote and smart sensing data products. The metadata catalogue also lists 117 services from participating organisations, and 12 VREs.

Tools and resources grouped by theme include:

- **Coordinate reference systems** - Services enabling geographical analysis through the use of coordinate reference systems.
- **Data management** - Services designed to cover the entire data lifecycle, from acquisition to visualisation.
- **Environmental monitoring** - Services enabling environmental monitoring and the evaluation of ecosystem health.
- **Functional traits** - Services analysing species' functional traits to determine their effect on processes and responses to environmental factors.
- **Habitats and ecosystems** - Services which provide information on habitat and biotope occurrence and characteristics.
- **Metagenomics** - Services dedicated to DNA Metabarcoding analysis.

- **Modelling** - Services which enable the derivation of future scenarios under multiple vectors of change.
- **Remote and smart sensing** - Services designed to cover the entire process (from selection, to downloading, to viewing and analysis) required to work with remote and smart sensing data products.
- **Semantics** - Services enabling discovery and interoperability and providing core and domain ontologies, as well as vocabularies and domain-relevant reference lists.
- **Species distribution and diversity** - Services designed to provide information on species distribution and coverage in different geographical areas.
- **Taxonomic** - Services which run taxonomic checks on scientific and common species names.

9.2 RI Data flows and services

9.2.1 Data workflows from long-term research sites

ICOS

ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System) is a European Research Infrastructure that aims to provide high-quality data on greenhouse gas emissions and sinks, and to support the development of policies and measures to mitigate climate change. ICOS produces quality-controlled observational data, results from modelling related to greenhouse gases, as well as synthesis reports. These data come from national measurement networks, from ICOS Thematic Centers and from modellers in the greenhouse gas research community. ICOS is organised along the Atmospheric, Ecosystem and Ocean Observational Networks, which are also organised as Thematic Centres (TC) collecting data on carbon and greenhouse gas fluxes across Europe. Data and data products are published and shared through the ICOS Carbon Portal²⁹. ICOS defines 4 data levels ranging from Raw data, Observation data (Level 0), Quality controlled near-real-time (NRT) data (Level 1, divided into two sub-levels dealing with Level 1 NRT data and Level 1 Internal working data), final quality checked data products (Level 2), and elaborated data products (Level 3) (ICOS, 2022; Vermeulen et al., 2020).

The data workflows of ICOS address several stages, including data acquisition, local and central quality control, processing, and publication of data and data products.

- **Data acquisition and submission:** Data are collected at the different observation stations related to the observational networks of the different domains. Data collection follows a clear protocol and method which enables the integration and central quality control of data. NRT data needs to be provided to the central ICOS facility (TC) within 24 hours after local (automated or manual) quality check (e.g., thresholds). This data is considered as raw and Level 0 data, being converted from engineer units to physical units. Sensors are centrally calibrated at regular intervals. Raw data are transferred directly to the ICOS Carbon Portal or via the TC ingested in real-time, minted a persistent identifier (e.g., handle PID) and stored in a safe repository (e.g., EUDAT B2SAFE). In order to ensure data consistency along the workflow, SHA256 checksums are calculated.
- **Data quality control and assurance:** NRT data provided by the observation stations are automatically and centrally quality controlled within 24 hours after the measurement to enable fast distribution of data. Raw data used as well as software, scripts and the result of the quality check process are stored as part of the provenance metadata. In addition, for the development of Level 2 data products, final quality checks are performed for a yearly complete time series.

²⁹ see <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/about-data-portal>

- Data processing and development of data products: NRT data are published after central quality control and assurance. Internal working data (IW) are generated for the development of Level 2 data products. Level 2 data are finally quality checked and integrated with an update frequency of at least once per year.
- Persistent Identification: Internal data are identified using a handle PID. Published and shared data (Level 1 NRT, Level 2, and Level 3) are published issuing a DataCite DOI and the related metadata. In addition, ORCIDs³⁰ for researchers and contributors and RORs³¹ are recommended for use.
- Data publication and sharing: Data and data products are shared via the ICOS Carbon Portal once the TC has approved the data. Data download and usage is tracked and provided via the portal. In addition, an open-source python library³² is provided to directly access metadata and data from the ICOS Carbon Portal.
- Data licensing: ICOS data is licensed under the Creative Common Attribution 4.0 licence (CC-BY 4.0 Int.)

Overall, the data workflows of ICOS are designed to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and accessibility of its data. By providing high-quality data on carbon and greenhouse gas fluxes, ICOS aims to support research, policymaking, and public awareness on climate change. Information on data levels and flows is provided via the website³³ and GitHub³⁴.

ACTRIS

ACTRIS³⁵ (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) is a fully established pan-European RI that focuses on short-lived atmospheric constituents and their interactions with the aim of improving our knowledge in atmospheric processes and our resilience to climate change and air quality. The ACTRIS network is composed of (1) observational platforms composed of measurement stations where aerosol, cloud, and trace gas measurements are performed in-situ as well as with remote sensing techniques (e.g., to build a profile through the troposphere and lower stratosphere); and (2) exploratory platforms, which are laboratory and mobile platforms used to perform dedicated experiments, but also simulation chambers where atmospheric processes can be analysed under controlled conditions. Due to the high data heterogeneity, the data are managed in five specific data management topic centres (centres of expertise), and then centralised and published in the “Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services unit”.

While there are substantial differences in the data workflows depending on the data types (and the associated topic centres), the main steps can be summarised as follows:

- Data collection and annotation: Raw data are collected and undergo a first quality and metadata check and annotation procedure at site (or national) level. An instrument-related calibration might already be applied at this level. Then, they are transferred to the topical centres of expertise.
- Calibration, quality assurance and control: If needed, the data are then calibrated using standardised procedures by the centre of expertise. The centre also applies QA/QC routines and prepares the data to be usable in further processing steps. The data are then transferred to the central data management centre.

³⁰ see <https://orcid.org>

³¹ see <https://ror.org>

³² see <https://github.com/ICOS-Carbon-Portal/pylib>

³³ see <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/data-collection/data-flow>

³⁴ see <https://github.com/ICOS-Carbon-Portal/>

³⁵ see <https://www.actris.eu/>

- Synthesised data products: The central data management centre generates higher level data products (e.g., by aggregation over space and/or time), synthesised data products combining several data sources (including external data sources), and model-based and statistical analyses.
- Publication and dissemination: The data products and metadata are then made available via the central data management centre and in accordance with the FAIR data principles.

A detailed description of the data management plan is available on GitHub³⁶ including the documentation of the data levels as well as schematic data flows.

FLUXNET

FLUXNET³⁷ (Pastorello et al., 2020) is a worldwide network of eddy covariance measurement sites collecting observational data of the carbon, water, and energy cycles between the biosphere and the atmosphere. It aims to improve the understanding of ecosystem functioning and to detect trends in climate, greenhouse gas concentrations, and air pollution. The observational data are processed, analysed, and published via regional networks, which are linked within FLUXNET. Measured scalars and fluxes are, for example, CO₂, CH₄, water vapour, sensible and latent heat, but also ancillary variables such as air temperature, precipitation, and radiation, which are necessary for the generation of high-level data products.

The data processing workflow is composed of the following main steps:

- Data collection and first quality control: Measurement data at high temporal frequency (e.g., half-hourly) are collected at the eddy covariance towers. Then, they undergo a first manual and automated quality control (e.g., visual check, spike detection) by the local site manager.
- Standardisation, quality control: The data are then transferred to the regional FLUXNET networks, where they are standardised and undergo a further, uniformized quality control.
- Production of high-level data products: added-value data products (gap filled flux partitioning data) are then generated at the regional network level using uniformised software packages.
- Dissemination: the data products are then archived and made available for distribution and download.

ICP Forests

The International Cooperative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests (ICP Forests)³⁸ is a collaborative effort between European countries and other regions, established to monitor the effects of air pollution on forests. The program collects data from various sources, including national forest inventory data, atmospheric deposition monitoring, and soil monitoring. These data are processed and analysed to derive insights into the state of forest health and the effects of air pollution. ICP Forest encompasses around 6000 Level I plots³⁹ focusing on tree crown condition, soil condition and foliar nutrient status of trees, and around 800 Level II plots⁴⁰ focusing on a broader range of sub-programmes. Around 90 forested eLTER sites are co-located with ICP Forests⁴¹ and providing data via the ICP Forest data workflows and submission.

³⁶ see <https://github.com/actris/data-management-plan/blob/master/DMP/ACTRIS-DMP.md>

³⁷ see <https://fluxnet.org/>

³⁸ see <http://icp-forests.net/>

³⁹ see <http://icp-forests.net/page/largescale-forest-condition>

⁴⁰ see <http://icp-forests.net/page/level-ii>

⁴¹ see https://deims.org/search/sites/lter?f%5B0%5D=network_ri_1%3AICP%20Forests

The data workflows of ICP Forests addresses different aspects:

- Data acquisition and submission: As part of the ICP Forests Programme data on e.g., forest inventory and health, atmospheric deposition, or soil are collected at national observation plots (Level I and II plots, with differing levels of observations) following a clear protocol in design and observation⁴². These data are collected by different agencies and organisations and are submitted to ICP Forests for processing and analysis on regular intervals, mainly with a yearly frequency as part of the data reporting.
- Data quality control and assurance: Basic quality control is performed on the level of the national data collectors applying the rules defined in the ICP Forest Manual. Before the data are processed, they undergo central quality control checks to ensure their accuracy and completeness performed by the ICP Forest Programme Centre. A number of rules are defined for the different sub-programmes⁴³. This includes checking for missing values, outliers, and inconsistencies. Only final quality checked data are ingested into the central database.
- Data processing and creation of data products: Submitted data with a monthly resolution (as reported by the national data collectors) are shared as data products. This can be considered as cleaned and quality controlled (Level 2) data. Raw and observation data (with original resolution) are managed and stored at the level of the different national data providers.
- Persistent identification and provenance: Currently no persistent identifiers are issued for the shared and published data. Internal database identifiers are used to identify and track provenance of data points and data.
- Data publication and sharing: Data from ICP Forest are shared using a download page after completing a data request to ICP Forest⁴⁴. This needs to be approved by the different data contributors. By having the data request forms data usage and type is tracked centrally by ICP Forest.

Overall, the data workflows of ICP Forests are designed to collect, process, and analyse data from various sources to derive insights into the state of forest health and the effects of air pollution. The program's data management and dissemination processes ensure that the data are of high quality and are accessible to stakeholders and policymakers.

ICP Integrated Monitoring

The International Cooperation Programme on Integrated Monitoring (ICP IM)⁴⁵ aims for an integrated monitoring of ecosystems and addresses the simultaneous measurement of physical, chemical, and biological properties of an ecosystem over time and across compartments at the same location. By this, ICP IM is strongly linked to the eLTER aims and many of the ICP IM sites also participate in eLTER. In practice, monitoring is divided into a number of compartmental sub-programmes which are linked by the use of the same parameters (cross-media flux approach) and/or same/close stations (cause-effect approach) and following a defined design and protocol⁴⁶. ICP IM is under the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). Currently, the programme centre (PC) of ICP IM is at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU).

⁴² see <http://icp-forests.net/page/icp-forests-manual>

⁴³ see <https://icp-forests.org/documentation/Tests/index.html>

⁴⁴ see <http://icp-forests.net/page/data-requests>

⁴⁵ see <https://www.slu.se/en/Collaborative-Centres-and-Projects/integrated-monitoring>

⁴⁶ see <https://www.slu.se/en/Collaborative-Centres-and-Projects/integrated-monitoring/monitoring-manual/>

Data management and workflows are organised along yearly data submissions with a central database at SLU.

- Data acquisition and submission: Data on the different sub-programmes of ICP IM are collected at the ICP IM monitoring stations, which are located across Europe. Data are managed and quality controlled by the single monitoring stations and are submitted on a yearly basis (depending on the sub-programme) to the PC following a defined submission workflow and data structure. Data are submitted on the level of monthly aggregations (for continuous measurements) and raw and observation data are stored locally at the different monitoring stations within their own data management environment.
- Quality check and assurance: Basic data quality control of the raw and observation data is done by the local monitoring stations before temporal aggregation and transformation into the data submission format. Submitted data are centrally quality controlled before storing into the central database. Issues on data quality are communicated with the data providers issuing a re-submission of data, if needed. Final quality-controlled data (Level 1 or 2) are stored in the central database and are used for analysis and modelling.
- Data processing and development of data products: ICP IM currently is not defining data products and data levels. Data from the local monitoring sites are submitted as temporal aggregates from observation data with a temporal resolution of a month. As these data are then centrally quality controlled and harmonised, they can be seen as level 2 data products, which are shared by the user community upon request.
- Persistent identification: No persistent identifier is used and data points and datasets are identified internally on the level of the database.
- Data publication and sharing: ICP IM shares data upon request requiring the data needs and the intended use of data. Currently no data portal is provided.

ICP Waters

ICP Waters is the International Cooperative Programme for assessment and monitoring of the effects of air pollution on rivers and lakes⁴⁷. The ICP Waters programme was established in 1985 with the specific objective of assessing the degree to which atmospheric pollution has affected surface waters, particularly with regard to issues such as acidification, heavy metals and Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs). ICP Waters operates from the middle of a monitoring hierarchy that is designed to evaluate the environmental effects of air pollutants on surface waters chemistry and biology, and predict future ecosystem changes occurring under different atmospheric deposition scenarios. Lower in the hierarchy is a series of national networks that employ progressively less comprehensive and frequent sampling but greater spatial coverage, culminating in one-time regional surveys. Achieving the Programme objectives requires that both the temporally intensive and regionally extensive data are collected on a continually basis.

The hierarchy of national monitoring programmes is thus reflected in the hierarchy of the ICP Waters programme to deal with:

- Level I: Data from small catchments, monthly or seasonal sampling;
- Level II: Relatively large number of sites with minimum annual sampling frequency;
- Level III: Regional surveys. Sampling of many sites one time in several years.

ICP Waters focuses on Level I, and deals with water chemical data from catchments with a sampling frequency from weekly to seasonal. With the less frequent sampling, the biological aspects become

⁴⁷ see <https://www.icp-waters.no/>

more important as they accumulate the effects of changing water quality in the previous period. Also, monitoring of sediments will provide possibilities for a coherent and comprehensive picture of the impact of long-range transboundary air pollution on the freshwater ecosystems. The Level II and III data are important in particular to illustrate the regional picture of acidification situation and to evaluate the representativeness of the more intensively monitored catchments.

The sampling campaigns are devoted to the freshwater ecosystems (rivers and lakes) where acidification, trace metals, and POPs are measured using chemical methods. The biological effects of acidification are monitored, and may be developed according to two categories: selecting species or communities of macrophytes, phytoplankton, microphytobenthon, zooplankton, macro-invertebrates, insects, and fish.

With a few exceptions, data processing for the various monitored aspects follows these steps:

- **Sampling:** the activity, dedicated to collecting the water sample or individuals belonging to different biological groups, must be in accordance with standard limnological methods and must be carried out in relation to the type of species or organisms to be collected for monitoring.
- **Analysis:** usually after collecting the sample, it must undergo an analysis action which differs according to the sample considered, always follows standard limnological protocols, and almost always involves the use of laboratory instrumentation (e.g., microscopes, spectrophotometers).
- **Quality assurance and quality control:** to ensure data quality and correct technical transfer of data, the data quality control action is according to the following: (i) looking for outliers, (ii) looking for continuity in time series. Use of blanks, standards, (certified) reference materials and/or regular participation in laboratory intercomparison are used.
- **Data reporting:** The water chemistry/biological analysis results are reported to the Programme Centre and stored in the ICP Waters database. In both cases, the results should be reported in a special form prepared as an excel-file. The reporting forms are available at the ICP Waters homepage⁴⁸. In the data reporting forms, harmonisation of parameter names is ensured through collaboration with the broader International Cooperative Programme (ICP).

TERENO

TERENO (TERrestrial ENVironmental Observatories)⁴⁹ is a German network of observation platforms funded by the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres that aims to investigate the consequences of global change on terrestrial ecosystems as well as their socio-economic implications. The observed time series (meteorological and hydrological data, water vapour and trace gas fluxes, etc.) are meant to be integrated with remote sensing and external data (biodiversity and socio-economic data, legacy data) into models and analysis tools. The resulting data products are aimed to derive efficient prevention, mitigation, and adaptation strategies of terrestrial ecosystems to global change. The platforms are grouped into four observatories representative of the major ecosystems in Germany. The infrastructure has been running since 2013.

Three data levels are defined in the TERENO data policy: (1) raw data are unprocessed or preliminary pre-processed data and data products without quality control; (2) quality-controlled data have passed quality control procedures; (3) derived products are derived from quality-controlled data and may include multiple-sensor data, researcher driven analysis and interpretation, and model-based interpretation using other data.

⁴⁸ see <http://www.icp-waters.no/>

⁴⁹ see <https://www.tereno.net/joomla/>

Only data complying to the TERENO data policy and data formats (based, when applicable, on ISO and/or OGC - Open Geospatial Consortium - standards) are made available on the decentralised data portal TEODOOR. However, only data that have undergone quality assurance and that are used or referenced in publications, are publicly available. Other data (raw, preliminary data, intermediate research results, etc.) can be uploaded to TEODOOR if they comply to the formats, but their availability is restricted, e.g., to project or TERENO members, and might be limited in time depending on the maturity level of the data. Published data have to be available for at least 15 years. They are related to the metadata catalogue via persistent URLs based on the metadata UID (Unique identifier) and have their own DOI (Digital Object Identifier). Documents on the TERENO data policy⁵⁰ and the data management plan⁵¹ are available online.

9.2.2 Data workflow from biodiversity initiatives

Data aggregators (GBIF, OBIS, WoRMS, DataONE, DiSSCo, ...)

For biodiversity data, metadata catalogues are not an optimal way to publish data for reuse. This is because there are so many species and species combinations worldwide, all of which can be of interest for a study or report, i.e., search criteria, and it is not often possible to list all species in a dataset separately in the metadata. For this reason, GBIF — the Global Biodiversity Information Facility — is the most important mechanism to expose data from diverse local sources to be findable as biodiversity data. The global service, i.e., GBIF.org acts as a data aggregator, and individual nodes (local infrastructures) manage and publish biodiversity data locally at national nodes level and then mobilise their data through the global portal (GBIF.org). The local node can also act as a national data aggregator and be a gateway to the global GBIF, which then draws the diverse data sources together through the use of data standards. Standards like EML, DarwinCore and its extensions form the basis for the bulk of GBIF.org's index of hundreds of millions of species occurrence records (see “Standards and vocabularies” section below).

There are also other thematic biodiversity data networks, which share or aggregate biodiversity data from a thematic perspective. OBIS (Ocean Biodiversity Information System) is a gateway to the world's ocean biodiversity and biogeographic data and information required to address pressing coastal and world ocean concerns. It provides the world's largest scientific knowledge base on the diversity, distribution, and abundance of all marine organisms in an integrated and standardised format. In addition to biodiversity data, OBIS facilitates the integration of biogeographic information with physical and chemical environmental data, to facilitate climate change studies.

Standards and vocabularies

As mentioned, in gbif.org and other thematic biodiversity data aggregators, data are made interoperable to be aggregated by using community standards, which define the syntax or data structure when exchanging data through APIs and vocabularies which transfer the unambiguous meaning of the data entities.

Biodiversity data are mostly transferred by using the DarwinCore (DwC) standard and its extensions, which are maintained and developed by the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)⁵² network. For metadata, GBIF uses the EML (Ecological Metadata Language) metadata schema which was developed and is maintained with support from the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS), a Center funded by the University of California Santa Barbara and the state of

⁵⁰ https://www.tereno.net/joomla/images/Resources/Downloads/TERENO-Data_Policy_2014-06-25.pdf

⁵¹ https://www.tereno.net/joomla/images/Resources/Downloads/Tereno-Data_management-plan-v10.pdf

⁵² see <https://www.tdwg.org/>

California. EML⁵³ is currently an open-source project and it is widely used by the global LTER community and DataONE. EML is widely used in Earth and environmental sciences, and in GBIF.org's biodiversity data, it is used to describe the circumstance metadata for the collected / observed species occurrences which constitute the lowest level of data in a biodiversity dataset.

Vocabularies are used with both of these standards (EML and DwC) quite freely, with the exception of controlled vocabularies embedded in the standards' mandatory fields, which are needed for indexing (meta)data in the global service. As biodiversity data can be originally collected for a variety of purposes, vocabularies play an important role in describing and documenting the raw data as accurately as possible. Richly documented data can be then aggregated to several networks, without losing the original purpose.

The most crucial "vocabulary" for GBIF is the species names, which can also be shared in gbif.org as its own data type (check-list data). The local check-lists, i.e., names vocabularies need to be mapped to the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy (GBIF Secretariat, 2022) which allows searching data by species (scientific) name and/or group in gbif.org.

Another important taxonomic check-list is World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS⁵⁴). It is to provide an authoritative and comprehensive list of names of marine organisms, including information (e.g., traits), synonymy, and the track changes in the taxon name.

Thematic nodes or biodiversity data sources can refer to or develop their own vocabularies, which enable enriching of raw data according to the theme.

GBIF

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) workflows concentrate on the data mobilising processes, and the actual research or modelling workflows are not part of the centralised global services. However, individual local nodes and RIs or virtual research environments, such as LifeWatch (ERIC) have developed many tools for QA, analysis, visualisation and documenting research workflows. The processes may be different depending on the richness and purpose of the original dataset. The global GBIF portal includes a catalogue of these tools. GBIF encourages data holders to publish the richest data possible to ensure their use across a wider range of research approaches and questions, but not every dataset includes information at the same level of detail. Sharing what is available through GBIF.org is valuable, because even partial information answers some important questions.

Four classes of datasets are currently supported by GBIF⁵⁵, namely (a) resources metadata, (b) check-list data, (c) occurrence data, and (d) sampling event data.

GBIF aggregates biodiversity data that can serve different purposes in the local sources. Hence, the local sources can use very different data formats, vocabularies, and QA procedures depending on the original purpose and kind of evidence collected to formulate/digitise the raw data. Examples of biodiversity occurrence data types include, e.g., collection data, DNA, image/sound files, remote sensing, human observation, literature observation.

- Data aggregation and publishing process at the data source. This includes creating or updating a dataset (this stage varies between nodes), publishing the data in a local database or by using GBIF's Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) (original purpose), and wrapping data into standard format

⁵³ see <https://eml.ecoinformatics.org/>

⁵⁴ see <https://www.marinespecies.org>

⁵⁵ see <https://www.gbif.org/dataset-classes>

(EML + DwC and extensions) creating a DarwinCore Archive DwC-A. Data can be enriched with external vocabularies at this point.

- Data processing and quality control: Because biodiversity observation data can originate from very different kinds of data sources and data may be originally collected for very different purposes (for example museum collections, DNA, sound or image files, citizen science, literature, etc.), GBIF.org does not require any particular level of data quality. Any level of data can be indexed in GBIF.org, and the quality needs to be expressed with DwC terms and also its extensions and by referring to external vocabularies (for example DwC MeasurementOrFact extension and vocabulary expressing). Once ingested, the dataset is split into individual records (fragmenting). The fragmented records referred to as “raw” are then individually identified to determine whether to create a new record or update an existing one. The content of each fragment is now normalised to Darwin Core terms, at which time the records are referred to as “verbatim”. Finally, the record goes through interpretation where quality control is also applied. For instance, this is where the taxonomic names are checked against the GBIF backbone. If there are gaps, e.g., a record only has a genus and species name, the higher taxonomic levels are added. If during interpretation, a mistake is noticed or we make an assumption, a flag is raised. On GBIF.org, the interpreted version of the record with issues (flags raised during interpretation) is shown, if any, but one can also view and compare with the verbatim version. The record is finally stored in a massive database.
- Persistent identification: Assigning a DOI for the newly registered dataset (or adopting the original DOI if the source has an independent contract with DataCite⁵⁶).
- Data product development and access: Data products can be provided as derived datasets and they can be assigned with a DOI. Derived datasets are citable records of GBIF-mediated occurrence data derived either from a GBIF.org data accessed through a cloud service, e.g., Microsoft AI for Earth (Azure), or data obtained by any means for which no DOI was assigned, but one is required (e.g., third-party tools accessing the GBIF search API).
- When created, a derived dataset is assigned a unique DOI that can be used to cite the data. To create a derived dataset authentication using a GBIF.org account is needed.
- Data publication and sharing: Once the record has been stored, maps, counters, and search indexes are updated. At this time, the record will be visible on GBIF.org and available for download. In addition, GBIF provides a RESTful JSON based API to access species, occurrences and maps⁵⁷. Data are provided as tab-delimited CSV and as Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A).

GBIF as a data aggregator does not specialise on any particular territory or habitat. National GBIF nodes can be represented by natural history museums, universities, governmental environment agencies, or sometimes there are also thematic nodes, which represent a specialised regional or global network (for example OBIS or VertNet). Many specialised data networks and platforms manage their own local databases and gain visibility by publishing data also through GBIF.org by using the same standards and data transfer protocols, but using specialised vocabularies that enable them to express discipline specific features of their data. Also, VREs like LifeWatch or BioDT can retrieve data from local nodes GBIF API or via GBIF.org API depending on how they need to select the data for their analyses.

⁵⁶ see <https://datacite.org/>

⁵⁷ see <https://api.gbif.org/v1/>

9.2.3 Data workflows from citizen science focusing on biodiversity

iNaturalist

iNaturalist⁵⁸ is a citizen science tool, i.e., an online social network of people sharing biodiversity information to help each other learn about nature. It is also a crowdsourced species identification system and an organism occurrence recording tool.

The basic unit of iNaturalist is observation. An observation records an encounter with an individual organism at a particular time and location. This includes encounters with signs of organisms like tracks, nests, or dead subjects. iNaturalist provides a place to add this information along with associated text, photos, and tags. The observations are stored in a PostgreSQL database, with heavy reliance on elasticsearch for search. Each user can upload their observations, as photos or sound and the flow for uploading observations involves these steps:

- **Collection:** concerns either the taking of one or more photos of the subject or the recording of a sound that is emitted by the subject, at a specific place and time.
- **Uploading:** involves uploading the sound or photos collected through the appropriate iNaturalist website or Apps.
- **Identifying and other annotation:** the photos and sound uploaded are accompanied by some information collected automatically by the device (e.g., date, latitude and longitude coordinates) and other information that can be added later to improve knowledge of the subject (e.g., membership of an iNaturalist project, if the subject is a captive or cultivated, dead or alive, male or female). Identification, i.e., the assignment of a taxonomic label to the subject, is one of the key elements for iNaturalist. This can be done either directly by the user just after uploading. If, however, the user is unable to make the identification directly, two processes can come into play: (i) the community of platform users who suggest the identification or (ii) an automatic image recognition process, which allows for a suggestion of the most probable taxon through the images already uploaded in iNaturalist and the georeferencing information present in the photo.
- **Quality assurance and quality control:** any uploaded observation is labelled “Needs ID” if it has a date, is georeferenced (i.e., has lat/lon coordinates), has photos or sounds, and is not of a captive or cultivated organism. In the case when more than 2/3 of identifiers agree on a taxon, the observation becomes “Research Grade”, otherwise it is voted as “Casual”. The user community is itself part of the quality control process.

All the observations collected in iNaturalist are shared by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) as part of the iNaturalist Research-Grade Observations dataset⁵⁹.

A characteristic workflow can be described as: observations are collected in the form of evidence for a species occurrence. The mobile application ingests images or sound files and extracts time and locality information from the exif-information of the ingested file (if allowed in the used device). The tool then offers machine learning aided identification of species (or species groups) and it has an inbuilt peer-review quality assurance mechanism for the species identification. The peer-reviewed observations and their evidence (image or sound file) and accompanying occurrence data are then ingested to gbif.org, from where the data can be accessed by any researcher.

The tool can also be used to collect observation via citizen science projects and contribute to gap filling or a monitoring scheme. In such a case, the project needs to inform the “citizen scientists”, i.e., participants on how to collect observations and the review process can be controlled by the project's

⁵⁸ see <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

⁵⁹ see <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/50c9509d-22c7-4a22-a47d-8c48425ef4a7>

experts. As of June 2018, iNaturalist offers three types of projects: Collection, Umbrella, and Traditional⁶⁰.

Umbrella projects are designed to collate, compare, or promote a set of existing projects. Within eLTER RI, two such projects were created: eLTER Platforms⁶¹ and eLTER-Italy network⁶². These projects allow to aggregate the citizen science observations about biodiversity, collected in different eLTER sites (LTSEr platforms and sites' Italy), as if they were collected for a single purpose.

eBird

eBird is a global, internet-based platform for collating observations of birds, and for birders to maintain records of their sightings. It is housed in Cornell University's Laboratory of Ornithology. eBird takes a novel approach to citizen science by developing cooperative partnerships among experts in a wide range of fields: population ecologists, conservation biologists, quantitative ecologists, statisticians, computer scientists, GIS and informatics specialists, application developers, and data administrators. The collected data are a powerful resource for a wide range of scientific questions. By building tools that engage the global birding community, eBird gathers unprecedented volumes of information on where and when birds are observed at high spatial and temporal resolutions. eBird documents the presence or absence of species, as well as bird abundance through checklist data. A web interface allows participants to submit their observations or view results via interactive queries of the database. Internet tools maintain personal bird records and enable users to visualise data with interactive maps, graphs, and bar charts. The resulting collaborative dataset is also available through gbif.org (<https://doi.org/10.15468/aomfmb>).

Zooniverse

Zooniverse⁶³ is a platform for people-powered research. The research is made possible by volunteers, who come together to assist professional researchers by using the mobile application and the platform. Each project is constructed with the aim of converting volunteers' efforts into measurable results. These projects have produced a large number of published research papers, as well as several open-source sets of analysed data. Zooniverse projects **cover all disciplines** starting from arts and history, but covering also nature and finally also more exact disciplines like physics or space. On the contrary to iNaturalist, in the Zooniverse platform, **volunteer community is not uploading data or materials**, but they are able to engage with a specific research goal or question, by using data provided by the researchers. This volunteer data classification mechanism gives the researcher new derived data to work with and helps progress science.

Workflow: In zooniverse the researcher uploads data to the tool, and creates a desired workflow for the volunteers to process and/or categorise the data. There are several workflow options that the researcher can choose, and process the data collaboratively together with the volunteers. So, the citizen science phase can be any step (or several of them) in the workflow.

⁶⁰ see <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/managing-projects>

⁶¹ see <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/eltser-platforms>

⁶² see <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/lter-italy-network>

⁶³ see <https://www.zooniverse.org/about>

9.2.4 Data workflows for socio-ecological science

CESSDA

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)⁶⁴ is a network of European social science data archives. It serves as a platform for the development of European integrated data services based on broad collaboration among national social science data archives across Europe. The CESSDA Consortium is currently composed of 21 member countries and one observer. Several European countries are in the process of becoming a CESSDA member or observer. CESSDA also has partners in a number of countries outside of the consortium.

The CESSDA archive is organised as a data catalogue, where data are accessible through discovery metadata (only). The CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) contains descriptions of more than 40,000 data collections held by CESSDA's Service Providers (SPs). Datasets come from over 20 European countries. It is a one-stop shop for searching and finding European social science data. The data described may be quantitative, qualitative or mixed-modes data, cross-sectional or longitudinal, recently collected or historical data. The metadata (study descriptions) are in whatever language they were provided by the organisations producing the metadata. Some publishers provide study descriptions both in English and in the local language, some only in either English or in the local language. Currently, about 75% of study descriptions are available in English.

Generally, socio-ecological data types deviate quite much compared to the data from other eLTER research challenges. The biggest deviation is that data generated in social sciences research can come from both quantitative and qualitative study settings. Notably, within the field of social sciences, data often originates from human participants. This means that the rules for handling (sensitive) personal data will deserve special attention in the workflows.

Workflows for sharing data through CESSDA are represented in the Data Management Expert Guide as data lifecycle phases, to ensure reproducibility (FAIRness) of the research. The lifecycle is divided into seven phases: 1) Plan, 2) Organise and document, 3) Process, 4) Store, 5) Protect, 6) Archive and publish, and 7) Discover. The phases suit well for describing also eLTER environmental data, with the exception of data anonymisation and protection, which is more clearly a requirement of sociological research data and other qualitative data that possibly contains personal information which falls under the European GDPR regulations.

Data processing before storing the data is crucial in providing the very heterogeneous data in an interoperable manner, also in a data repository. This is why the CESSDA data management expert guide gives detailed instructions and rationale for processing the data before storing and publishing the metadata. The processing guidelines instruct how to ensure data integrity, and create documentation so that the integrity of data is not lost in data transfer or sharing. Also, categorisation, e.g., coding of quantitative and qualitative data, is explained and instructed. Special attention is given to statistical techniques regarding processing of survey data⁶⁵. The CESSDA Data Catalogue⁶⁶ and its documentation (including APIs) provides an overview on the available data. There is also a beta version of the more technical CESSDA Data Archival Guide (DAG)⁶⁷, which gives more detailed information about how participant organisations should manage the data being archived to CESSDA.

⁶⁴ see <https://www.cessda.eu/>

⁶⁵ see <https://dmeg.cessda.eu/>

⁶⁶ see <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/about>

⁶⁷ see <https://dag.cessda.eu/>

10 Annex C - Access of workflows on GitHub

All diagrams in this deliverable have been collected in a eLTER-RI GitHub repository at this link: <https://github.com/eLTER-RI/eLTER-workflow-diagrams>.

10.1 Upload new diagram in the GitHub

1. Export from Google diagrams.net the flow(s) in XML format.
2. Upload the XML file(s) to a GitHub repository.

10.2 Edit diagram store in the GitHub

1. Use [draw.io](https://app.diagrams.net/?src=github) desktop app or web app (<https://app.diagrams.net/?src=github>).
2. Select "Open Existing Diagram".

3. Select repo GitHub where diagram XML file is stored.

4. Select a diagram XML file.

5. Edit it with draw.io.

6. Save and commit the changes.

